

Communication over an Unknown Channel via Common Broadcasting

Thesis submitted for the degree “Doctor of Philosophy”

by

Nadav Shulman

Submitted to the Senate of Tel Aviv University

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Department of Electrical Engineering - Systems

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This research was conducted at the
Department of Electrical Engineering - Systems,

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Abstract

In this study we consider the problem of communication over an unknown channel. Some new concepts for the broadcast channel, which can model unknown channels, are introduced and a collection of problems related to universal communication are investigated.

The novel concepts for the broadcast channel we introduce, are focused on scenarios where the same, common information should be transmitted to all receivers. The first concept is termed “static broadcasting”, and relates to a case where common finite information (such as a data file) is transmitted to all receivers, and the rate for each receiver is defined as the data length divided by the time the receiver needs to be “online” to reliably decode the information. The second concept considers scenarios where there is a common endless stream of data to be transmitted to all receivers, and we look at the possible rate at which each receiver can sequentially reconstruct this stream. For these new settings, coding theorems and capacity region are found.

Motivated by the “static broadcasting” approach, we have developed a universal sequential decoding algorithm, based on a universal erasure decoder. For discrete memoryless channels the universal sequential decoder is capable of reliably decoding the data no matter what is the actual underlying channel. Furthermore, the decoding rate tends to the mutual information induced by the code prior and the channel conditional probability, as the size of the information message grows. The universal sequential decoder also enables reliable communication in scenarios where the rate is not known in advance, and moreover, there is no expectancy for the effective working rate. For example, when there is an unknown amount of side information at the receiver and when the size of the information message is unknown. For all these settings the universal sequential decoder achieves the best rate that can be expected.

Another difficulty that occurs in communication over an unknown channel is that a code with optimal symbol distribution cannot be designed when the capacity achieving prior is unknown. For this we consider the “universal prior” problem, i.e., how to determine a single input distribution that is appropriate for all channels. We show that for the class of all memoryless discrete input channels, the uniform prior is the appropriate universal prior in a max-min sense. Furthermore, we derive bounds on the absolute and relative rate degradation when the uniform prior is used instead of the capacity achieving prior, and show that at least for binary input channels this degradation is very small.

When communication is performed over an unknown channel, it may turn out that the channel capacity is very small. Low capacity channels require codes with long codewords. The complexity of creating, encoding and decoding long codes may be prohibitive. We show that in the case of low rate codes, we can use periodic codes without significant loss in the achievable transmission rate.

The collection of results presented in this study provides a basis for both theoretical understanding and practical solutions of various aspects and problems associated with communication over an unknown channel.

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List of Symbols and Notations

DMC	Discrete Memoryless Channel
\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{Y}	Discrete sets, e.g., DMC input and output alphabet sets
\mathcal{X}^n	Set of n -length sequences of elements of \mathcal{X}
\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}	Vectors such as codeword, or received sequence, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}^n$
$ \mathcal{X} $	Number of elements in the set \mathcal{X}
P, Q	Distributions over discrete set
U	Uniform distribution over the relevant set
W, V	Conditional distributions, DMC law
\log, \exp_2	Logarithm and exponent of base 2, i.e., $\log x = \log_2 x$ and $\exp_2\{x\} = 2^x$
$a \log \frac{a}{b}$	Equals 0 if $a = 0$, and $+\infty$ if $a > b = 0$
$H(X), H(P)$	Entropy of the random variable X , of the distribution P $H(P) = \sum_x -P(x) \log P(x)$
$h(p)$	Binary entropy. $h(p) = -p \log p - (1 - p) \log(1 - p)$
$I(X; Y)$	Mutual information between the random variables X and Y . $I(X; Y) = \sum_{x,y} \Pr(X = x, Y = y) \log \frac{\Pr(Y=y X=x)}{\Pr(Y=y)}$
$I(P; W)$	Mutual information between two random variables whose joint distribution is defined by P and W
$H(\mathbf{x}), I(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{y})$	Entropy of the empirical distribution of \mathbf{x} and the mutual information of the joint empirical distribution of \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y}
$C, C(W)$	Capacity of the channel W , $C(W) = \max_P I(P; W)$

$D(Q P)$	Divergence $D(Q P) = \sum_x Q(x) \log \frac{Q(x)}{P(x)}$
$D(V W Q)$	Conditional divergence $D(V W Q) = \sum_x Q(x) D(V(\cdot x) W(\cdot x))$
EX, \bar{X}	Expectation of the random variable X
$ x ^+$	$\max\{0, x\}$
$\lceil x \rceil$	Minimal integer greater or equal to x
$\lfloor x \rfloor$	Maximal integer smaller or equal to x
\sum_x	Convention - sum over all possible values of x
\square	End of proof

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Chapter 1

Introduction

In this study we examine the problem of universal communication. Universal communication considers situations where the statistics of the communication channel and possibly other components in the communication scenario are only partially known, if at all. The problem is to construct a communication scheme that is independent of the unknown channel characteristics, yet attains good performance, both in terms of rate and reliability, compared to a system designed with knowledge of the channel.

The general problem of (two terminal) universal communication can be stated as follows: The channel over which transmission is conducted is only known to belong to some family of channels. What are the bounds for the achievable rate and error probability, and what kind of communication algorithms can be used in such channels? This study is focused on memoryless settings.

Our investigation of the universal communication problem is motivated by the success of universal *source* coding [7, 12, 28, 85, 87, 88], which in many situations, essentially demonstrated that lack of knowledge of the source characteristics does not cause degradation (asymptotically) in the achievable compression rate. There are two basic concepts in universal source coding that we try to follow in this study. The first is that in universal source coding the rate is not predetermined, i.e., it is adapted according to the underlying source - “variable rate coding”. The second is the broad acceptance that source coding is used for fixed, one-shot, finite data, e.g., file compression.

One approach suggested previously for dealing with communication over un-

known channels is to design *universal decoders*, in which the decoder tries to attain the performance of decoders that are tuned to the channel [18, 27]. The comparison analysis focuses on the achieved rate and error probability. Since in the universal decoding scenario the code and its rate are the same regardless of the actual channel, the encoder is not optimal for each possible channel. In particular, there are channels for which the code rate may be greater than the channel capacity, leading to a high error probability even if the optimal maximum likelihood (ML) decoder is used, a fortiori, if a universal decoder is used.

Another approach previously suggested for universal communication is to look at transmission over an unknown channel as broadcasting to the various possible channels [11, 14]. While this approach may yield higher transmission rates for the better channels, it generally does not achieve the optimal rate for the true channel. Furthermore, it assumes that the decoder knows the channel's parameters.

In general, feedback may exist. Feedback enables the encoder to “learn” the channel and to change the encoding method accordingly. In this manner, adaptation to the encoding scheme and modification of the rate can take place [37, 49]. Feedback also enables the encoder and decoder to be synchronized to the state of the transmission and to implement sequential decoding schemes that may be simpler and yield smaller error probability [10].

Practical systems generally overcome the channel uncertainty obstacle by robustness which is realized by worst-case implementation and by channel estimation. An example of worst-case design is signal shaping [43], which in many cases aims to create a code with a Gaussian-like distribution which is the prior derived from worst-case analysis of power-limited additive channels. Channel estimation is done by using training sequences that enable learning of the correct channel parameters [38], or blind-equalization that enables fine tuning to the real channel along with information retrieval [8]. The channel estimation is not exact, resulting a mis-match decoding [21, 47, 54]. Additionally, practical systems use channel codes that are efficient to encode and decode [9, 42, 63].

This work combines the different approaches to yield a novel method of universal communication. The encoder's lack of information about the channel is

solved by “broadcasting” to all possible channels. The decoder, using a universal sequential decoder (when it does not know the channel), determines the effective working rate. Encoding and decoding complexity of unlimited length codes are handled by periodic codes. The optimal code “shaping”, i.e., the universal code prior, is found under the worst-case analysis.

An example for finite communication over an unknown channel is the Internet. Each server (encoder), or even each specific resource in it, can be viewed as a source of finite information. This block of data is to be transmitted to a client (decoder) when the parameters of the connection between it and the server, such as the rate and the packet loss probability, are not known in advance. The approach suggested in this thesis can be applied for this application.

1.1 Background

This section provides an overview of the topics which are related and required as background for this study.

Universal decoding

Results on universal decoding have been derived by many previous studies.

The maximum mutual information (MMI) decoder introduced by Goppa [34], makes no use of the channel statistics. This decoder determines that the transmitted message was \mathbf{x} , if it maximizes the *empirical* mutual information between it and the received message \mathbf{y} , $I(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{y})$. Csiszár and Körner [18, 19] showed that for discrete memoryless channels (DMCs) and constant composition codes, the MMI decoder attains the same random coding error exponent [30] as the optimal, ML decoder. In the case of additive channels, it was shown [16] that a minimum entropy decoder, which minimizes the noise empirical entropy $H(\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{x})$, has a similar performance when linear codes are used.

Other decoding schemes have been derived [27, 86] and were proved to work well for channels with memory, i.e., the resulting error exponent is the same as the random coding error exponent achieved by the ML decoder that knows the channel.

Worst-case analyses of unknown channels have been made in the scope of arbitrary varying channel [76] and compound channels [19]. Basically, the rate is bounded by the worst channel, i.e., good performance is guaranteed for rates bounded as follows: $R \leq \max_{P(X)} \min_{W \in \mathcal{W}} I(P; W)$, where \mathcal{W} is the collection of all possible channels.

Feedback channels and sequential decoding

It is well known that feedback, even noiseless, does not increase the capacity of a DMC [66]. Generally speaking, feedback can increase the capacity of a given channel with memory [13] and may also increase the channel's zero-error capacity [35].

Nevertheless, feedback may be used with DMC to improve the error probability using various schemes, most of which are sequential. General analysis of sequential decision can be found in [82]. Burnashev [10] has shown that for a DMC W with noiseless feedback the best achievable error exponent is $E_f(R) = C_1(1 - \frac{R}{C})$, where C is the channel's capacity and $C_1 = \max_{x_1, x_2} \sum_y W(y|x_1) \log \frac{W(y|x_1)}{W(y|x_2)}$. This error exponent is better than the error exponent without feedback [51]. The code suggested in [10], like most others codes that utilize feedback, contains sequential decoding, which leads to a random length code where the length depends on the noise pattern of the specific channel. Hence, these codes are block-to-variable codes.

An additional significant advantage of feedback is that it enables simple coding algorithms. Ahlswede [1] proposed the following iterative algorithm: Send the information as is (adapted to the channel's input), \mathbf{x} . Both decoder and encoder receive the channel's output \mathbf{y} . Now, the encoder compresses \mathbf{x} with respect to \mathbf{y} and sends it, again, through the channel. Each such iteration decreases the amount of transmitted data by a factor of $\sim \frac{H(X|Y)}{H(X)}$. After several such iterations, the encoder will have only few bits to send. These bits can be encoded with regular, low rate, good code. The obtained rate is $I(X; Y)$, which equals the channel's capacity if a suitable prior on X is chosen. The decoding is done backwards, from the end to the beginning of the received sequence.

Horstein [40] proposed a sequential algorithm for binary symmetric channels (BSC) with full, noiseless, feedback. The encoder uses the full feedback to attain the exact decoder's state and it "directs" the decoder (through the noisy channel) to the correct word, and to recover from decoding errors. This algorithm, which resembles arithmetic source coding, can be expanded to general DMCs [39]. For some DMCs it was shown that Horstein's algorithm can be viewed as a simple repeat-on-error coding scheme [64, 78].

Ooi and Wornell [56, 57] introduced a universal encoding scheme with feedback based on Ahlswede's iterative algorithm and the use of universal (conditional) source coder. In their scheme, all possible channels must pass some "minimal quality criterion", e.g., their capacity must be above some $\epsilon > 0$. The reason is that some components of the proposed scheme were designed for the worst possible channel.

The above schemes work with full noiseless feedback. There are several schemes that use only low rate signaling over the (possibly noiseless) feedback, e.g., "decision-feedback" and "automatic-repeat-request" (ARQ) [41]. Convolutional codes [23, 80, 81], in the presence of feedback, have ARQ decoding scheme extensions as well, which improve the decoding complexity and the error probability [36, 46, 83].

Viterbi [79] studied the effect of sequential decision feedback on communication over the Gaussian channel. Teletar and Gallager [77] investigated multiaccess channels with side information. They demonstrated a sequential decoding approach which utilizes the side information for handling the lack of a priori knowledge of the channel noise.

Erasure decoding

In general, decoders can have some indication of the "quality" of their decision. For example, the maximum a posteriori (MAP) decoder, which equals the ML decoder under the assumptions that all codewords are equiprobable, knows the exact error probability of its estimation. Hence, we may let the decoder declare "detected error", or *erasure*, if the channel output does not permit a sufficiently

reliable estimate of the transmitted codeword. For example, a MAP decoder can declare “erasure” or “detected error” whenever its estimation has less than 99.999% chance of being correct. Forney [41] has found the optimal decision regions for ML/MAP erasure decoders. Csiszár and Körner [18, 19] introduced a *universal* erasure decoder.

In the presence of feedback, erasure decoding can be used in schemes such as ARQ - whenever an erasure is detected, the decoder asks the encoder to retransmit the last codeword. If the block code rate is R , and the probability for erasure is ϵ , this scheme leads to an effective rate of $\frac{R}{1-\epsilon}$. Tuning the parameters in such a way that ϵ is small may yield a significant improvement in the error probability with virtually no change in the effective communication rate [41].

Broadcast channel

A broadcast channel, in which the codeword is transmitted to several decoders via different channels, has a capacity region which describes all possible *simultaneous* achievable rates that can be transmitted reliably. Broadcasting to two receivers is the most extensively studied case. A rate triplet (R_0, R_1, R_2) is achievable if there is a reliable coding scheme that sends common information to both receivers at rate R_0 in addition to private information sent to each receiver at rate R_1 and R_2 , respectively. In general the capacity region is unknown except for special cases such as degraded channels, where R_2 equals zero [11], degraded-like channels [32] and “degraded message set” problem, where it is desired to send private information only to one of the receivers [45].

It was pointed out that the broadcast channel can be used as a model for the compound or unknown channel, in which the different possible channels are treated as if they were different channels to broadcast on. Thus, the broadcast code is essentially a universal channel code. Assuming the decoder *knows* the channel’s parameters, the achievable rate may depend on the actual channel. Hence if the channel is less noisy, a higher rate can be achieved [11, 65].

Against this backdrop however, a fundamental problem arises when the same information needs to be transmitted on any possible underlying channel. To see

this, consider any degraded broadcast channel. At some point we will have to send to the degraded, slower decoder some information that the faster decoder already has. This causes rate degradation to the latter decoder. This example motivated us to consider a new setting for the broadcast channel.

1.2 Thesis Outline

In Chapter 2 we introduce a novel concept for the broadcast channel. We examine the scenario where only finite common data is to be transmitted to all receivers, and we allow each receiver to disconnect from the transmission whenever it wishes. The rate is calculated according to the time each receiver is “online”. Capacity region, coding theorem and bounds on the error probability are derived for this setting.

Chapter 3 begins with an analysis of sequential decoding of the erasure channel, which demonstrates communication without a *pre-known* working rate. Then, a universal sequential decoder is developed. We show that the universal sequential decoder is capable of reliably decoding the transmitted finite information no matter what the actual underlying DMC. Furthermore, the decoding rate tends to the mutual information derived by the code prior and the channel conditional probability, as the information message grows. While the main analysis is for IID code, in Appendix B a similar analysis is done for *almost* constant composition code.

The universal sequential decoder enables reliable communication in scenarios where the rate is not known in advance, and moreover, there is no expectancy for the effective working rate. In Chapter 4 several additional scenarios in which the rate is not known in advance are examined. This includes an unknown amount of side information at the decoder and communication scheme over an unknown channel, where the size of information message is unknown.

In Chapter 5, the problem of “universal prior” is handled. When the code should be designed without the knowledge of the channel, some of its parameters, such as the code prior should be chosen appropriately. We show that the uniform prior is the one that should be used if the channel is known only to have discrete

input. Bounds on the maximum absolute and relative rate degradation when the uniform prior is used instead of the capacity achieving prior are found and shown to be very small for binary input channels.

When communication is performed over an unknown channel, it may turn out that the channel capacity is infinitely small. Hence the use of codes with infinite length is required. The complexity of creating, encoding and decoding long codes may be prohibitive. In Chapter 6 we show that in the case of low rate codes, we can use periodic codes without significant loss in the achievable transmission rate.

In Chapter 7 we go back to the broadcast channel and present yet another new concept for broadcasting common information. This time we look at infinite information that should be received in a streamable way. Although this chapter is somewhat unrelated to the problem of universal communication, it is a natural continuation of the broadcasting concept introduced in Chapter 2.

In Chapter 8 we summarize the study and present a collection of points for possible future research.

Chapter 2

Static Broadcasting

2.1 The Concept of Static Broadcasting

The communication scenario considered in the classical broadcast channel [11] assumes the following situation. A single sender transmits information simultaneously to many receivers. The transmitter and all the receivers are synchronously connected along all communication time. The main problem is to find the collection (region) of simultaneously achievable rates to each subset of the receivers. A fundamental result states that it is possible to transmit at a higher rate than achieved by using time-sharing between the receivers. In the case of two receivers, we are looking at the achievable triplets (R_0, R_1, R_2) , each triplet indicates that common information can be sent to both receivers at rate R_0 , in addition to “private” information sent to each receiver at rate R_1 and R_2 , respectively. In a typical situation, there is common information that must be transmitted to all receivers. Under the classical broadcast channel scenario, a receiver that listens to the transmitted information through a better channel can get more information than the other receivers. The capacity region in this case defines the highest possible extra information rate to the better receiver.

Suppose, however, that we only have common information and that there is no extra information to be transmitted to the better receiver(s). In the classical broadcast scenario, the maximum possible rate at which this common information can be transmitted is determined by the “worst” channel. This scenario is widely handled under the *compound* channel settings, see [48] and reference therein. The

better channels have to “listen” to redundant information. Clearly, there must be a better solution.

In this chapter we define and analyze the *static broadcasting* setting. In this broadcasting scenario, the sender has only fixed common information it must transmit to all receivers. We suggest the following definition of the rate - the number of reliably received bits divided by the number of symbols the receiver has *used* to retrieve these bits (or, divided by the information gathering time). Under this definition, in principle, a receiver that listens through a better channel may gather fewer channel symbols in order to estimate the transmitted message, and thus increase its rate. In the time saved, it can, e.g., fetch more information from other transmitters. The term *static broadcasting* comes from the notion that the core information sent by the transmitter is fixed, static, needed for all receivers, and does not change [71]. For example, a specific data file has to be transmitted via a satellite channel to many receivers, when each has different noise characteristics.

We define the capacity region of the static broadcast channel and prove a coding theorem (direct and converse) for it. Interestingly, as explained below, the capacity region may be nonconvex, since the notion of time-sharing is not valid in this setting. In addition, we discuss the structure of good codes that can attain this capacity.

2.2 Capacity Region and Coding Theorem

In this study, a broadcast channel is composed of single transmitter and d discrete memoryless channels¹ W_i , $1 \leq i \leq d$. All channels have a common input alphabet, \mathcal{X} , and may have different output alphabets $\mathcal{Y}_1, \dots, \mathcal{Y}_d$, respectively. Through these channels, the transmitter broadcasts to d receivers. A code for transmitting $K = \log_2 M$ bits to all d receivers where the i th receiver uses n_i symbols, is an encoding method from a message $1 \leq j \leq M$ to a codeword of length $N =$

¹In the static broadcasting scenario, as in classical broadcasting, the capacity region depends only on the marginal distribution of the channels and not on the joint distribution, e.g., $W(y_1, y_2|x)$. This can be easily derived from the proof of the coding theorem to follow.

$\max_{1 \leq i \leq d} n_i$, i.e., $\mathcal{C} : \{1, \dots, M\} \rightarrow \mathcal{X}^N$, and d decoding methods, where the i th decoder, $\phi_i : \mathcal{Y}_i^{n_i} \rightarrow \{1, \dots, M\}$, estimates the message from the first n_i symbols at the i th channel output, $\hat{j}_i = \phi_i(\mathbf{y}_i)$. The rate of this code is (R_1, R_2, \dots, R_d) , where $R_i = K/n_i$. The average error probability associated with this code at the i th receiver is denoted by $P_e(\mathcal{C}, \phi_i, W_i)$. Under the assumption that all messages are equiprobable we have

$$P_e(\mathcal{C}, \phi_i, W_i) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M Pr\{j \neq \phi_i(\mathbf{y}_i) | \mathbf{x} = \mathcal{C}(j), W_i\} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M 1 - W_i(\phi_i^{-1}(j) | \mathcal{C}(j)),$$

where $\phi_i^{-1}(j) = \{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{Y}_i^{n_i} | \phi(\mathbf{y}) = j\}$ and $W(A | \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}^n) = \sum_{\mathbf{y} \in A} \prod_{t=1}^n W(y_t | x_t)$.

The static broadcast capacity region is defined as the closure of the set of all possible achievable rates. A rate (R_1, R_2, \dots, R_d) is said to be achievable if for any $\epsilon > 0$ there exists a code \mathcal{C} at this rate, such that $P_e(\mathcal{C}, \phi_i, W_i) < \epsilon$ for all i .

Theorem 2.1. *For a set of channels $W_1 \dots W_d$ with a common input alphabet \mathcal{X} , the rate (R_1, R_2, \dots, R_d) is in the static broadcast capacity region iff, for any $\delta \geq 0$ there exists K large enough and input priors P_1, P_2, \dots such that for all $1 \leq i \leq d$ and $n_i = \lfloor \frac{K}{R_i} \rfloor$*

$$\frac{1}{n_i} \sum_{t=1}^{n_i} I(P_t; W_i) \geq R_i - \delta. \quad (2.1)$$

Proof. The proof of the Theorem is quite straight forward. The converse is essentially the standard converse of the channel coding theorem, implemented over the portion of the received symbols of each receiver. As for the direct part, we use a random code, drawn according to the chosen priors. It is easy to see that the random coding technique by Gallager [30] can be generalized for a choice of an input probability that is independent but not necessarily identically distributed, and that the error probability can be bounded for each receiver, based on its portion of received data.

More precisely, taking Gallager's bound for the error probability over a channel defined by $\mathbf{W}_N(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x})$ and a code randomly chosen with probability $\mathbf{P}_N(\mathbf{x})$:

$$\bar{P}_e \leq 2^{\rho NR} \sum_{\mathbf{y}} \left[\sum_{\mathbf{x}} \mathbf{P}_N(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{W}_N(\mathbf{y} | \mathbf{x})^{1/(1+\rho)} \right]^{1+\rho}$$

for any $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$. Substituting $\mathbf{W}_N(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x}) = \prod_n W(y_n|x_n)$ and $\mathbf{P}_N(\mathbf{x}) = \prod_n P_n(x_n)$ yields a bound on the error exponent

$$-\frac{1}{N} \log \bar{P}_e \geq \max_{0 \leq \rho \leq 1} E_0(\rho, W, \mathbf{P}_N) - \rho R \quad (2.2)$$

where $E_0(\rho, W, \mathbf{P}_N) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_n E_0(\rho, W, P_n)$ and

$$E_0(\rho, W, P) = -\log \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} \left(\sum_{x \in \mathcal{X}} P(x) W(y|x)^{1/(1+\rho)} \right)^{1+\rho}. \quad (2.3)$$

Hence, using the properties of $E_0(\rho, W, P)$, see [30], the error exponent in (2.2) is positive for any rate R which satisfies

$$R < \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N I(P_n; W).$$

The average, over the random codes, of the error probability decays exponentially with K , and given that we are looking at a finite set of d channels, there exists a deterministic specific code with error probability up to d times the error probability of the random code average for each of the channels. \square

If the number of possible channels, d , is infinite, the above proof does not show the existence of a code that is simultaneously good for all channels. This issue will be reviewed at the end of the chapter.

In determining the boundaries of the capacity region, we look for the largest rates that satisfy (2.1). As $I(P; W)$ is a concave function of P , a point (R_1, \dots, R_d) on the boundary of the capacity region is attained with a sequence of priors P_t that change in time only after one of the receivers “quits listening”, i.e., $P_{t+1} = P_t$ if t does not belong to $\{n_1, \dots, n_d\}$.

For the different points inside the capacity region, bounds on the error probability of each decoder can be found. In the proof above there is a simple derivation of an upper bound for these probabilities. As in [77], accumulating $E_0(\rho, W_i, P_t)$ along the relevant time interval will lead to such a bound. More precisely, there is a code \mathcal{C} such that the error probability when using an ML decoder is bounded for each channel i by

$$P_e(\mathcal{C}, \phi_i, W_i) \leq d \min_{0 \leq \rho \leq 1} 2^{\rho K - \sum_{t=1}^{n_i} E_0(\rho, W_i, P_t)}.$$

2.3 Examples of the Capacity Region

A general method for finding the capacity region for static broadcasting with two receivers is as follows. Assume the two channels are W_1 and W_2 , and the corresponding capacities are C_1 and C_2 . As noted previously, while both receivers listen, the input prior, P , should be kept constant. After one of the receivers gets all the information, it quits. Now, in order to maximize the rate to the second receiver, the input prior should be changed to attain the capacity of this receiver's channel. Assuming we are sending K information bits and that $I(P; W_1) > I(P; W_2)$, then n_1 , the online time of the first receiver, and $n_2 - n_1$, the additional time that the second receiver stays online, satisfy:

$$K = n_1 I(P; W_1)$$

$$K = n_1 I(P; W_2) + (n_2 - n_1) C_2$$

which yield the effective rates:

$$R_1 = \frac{K}{n_1} = I(P; W_1) \tag{2.4}$$

$$R_2 = \frac{K}{n_2} = \frac{I(P; W_1) C_2}{C_2 + I(P; W_1) - I(P; W_2)}. \tag{2.5}$$

Of course, all the points (r_1, r_2) such that $r_1 \leq R_1$ and $r_2 \leq R_2$ are in the capacity region. To obtain the complete capacity region, we should take the union of the regions above over all possible values of the input prior, P .

When the capacity achieving prior is the same for all channels, their point-to-point capacity can be achieved simultaneously. For example, assume two binary symmetric channels. One is clean and the other has a crossover probability ε , i.e., $C_1 = 1$ and $C_2 = 1 - h(\varepsilon)$. The classical broadcast capacity region for this channel [11] is

$$R_0 = 1 - h(u(1 - \varepsilon) + (1 - u)\varepsilon) \tag{2.6}$$

$$R_1 = h(u)$$

$$R_2 = 0,$$

where the parameter u can take any value between 0 and 1.

Now consider the following communication technique. Take any good systematic code for the noisy channel. The systematic part (the information bits are the prefix of each codeword) is sufficient, of course, for the noiseless channel and leads to an effective rate of 1 for that channel. The noisy channel receives the information at a rate determined by the code. Figure 2.1 depicts the capacity regions of both the classical broadcast and the static broadcast settings. The region for the regular (classical) broadcast setting is depicted as $R_0 + R_1$ vs. $R_0 + R_2$.

Figure 2.1: Static broadcast capacity region for two BSCs with different crossover probabilities. Classical broadcast capacity region indicated with dashed line.

The capacity region of the classical broadcast channel is convex as time-sharing can always be used in order to obtain any rate-point that lies on a line between two achievable rate-points. In the static broadcasting approach, time-sharing between two strategies is not a valid strategy. Hence, the capacity region is not necessarily convex.

An example for a nonconvex capacity region is the following “two language speaker” channel [15]. Suppose there is a speaker (transmitter) who knows two languages, Hebrew and Japanese, and two listeners (receivers), each knowing a different language. Denote by \mathcal{H} and \mathcal{J} the collections of words the speaker knows in Hebrew and Japanese, respectively. Thus, the channel’s input alphabet

is $\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{H} \cup \mathcal{J}$, and the channel law is

$$W_1(y|x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = x \text{ and } x \in \mathcal{J} \\ 1 & \text{if } y = ? \text{ and } x \in \mathcal{H} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$W_2(y|x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = x \text{ and } x \in \mathcal{H} \\ 1 & \text{if } y = ? \text{ and } x \in \mathcal{J} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$$

where ‘?’ represents an unrecognized word. Following (2.4) and (2.5), this broadcast channel yields a nonconvex static broadcasting capacity region described in Figure 2.2 where we assumed that the speaker knows 31 words in each language.

Figure 2.2: Static broadcast capacity region of a speaker of two languages. Regular broadcast capacity region indicated with dashed line.

The achieved regular broadcast capacity region (including common information) for this channel is defined by

$$R_1 + R_0 \leq I(P; W_1) \quad \text{and} \quad R_2 + R_0 \leq I(P; W_2)$$

where P may be any input distribution. In both the classical and static broadcasting we can see that by utilizing the convexity of the mutual information, we may look only at input distributions such that in each language the words are equiprobable, and the only free parameter is the probability to use Japanese (or Hebrew). The gain in the capacity region in the regular broadcast channel with respect to the time sharing-between the two languages is due to the ability to code some information by the *order* of the used language [15].

Consider a modification of the channel above such that any listener unexpectedly receiving a word in an unfamiliar language is totally confused, i.e., $\mathcal{Y}_1 = \mathcal{J}$, $\mathcal{Y}_2 = \mathcal{H}$ and

$$W_1(y|x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = x \text{ and } x \in \mathcal{J} \\ |\mathcal{J}|^{-1} & \text{if } x \in \mathcal{H} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$
$$W_2(y|x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y = x \text{ and } x \in \mathcal{H} \\ |\mathcal{H}|^{-1} & \text{if } x \in \mathcal{J} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The regular broadcasting region is simply the region produced by time-sharing between the two listeners, while the static broadcast approach enables, inherently, queuing. Hence the Japanese listener can be served at full speed (its capacity) and after that the Hebrew listener is served at capacity rate, however its effective rate is slower as the Hebrew listener had to wait first for the Japanese to be served. Figure 2.3 shows the capacity region for this channel with 32 words in each of the languages.

2.4 Bounds on the Error Probability

We now examine the probability of erroneous decoding in the static broadcasting scheme. Although the proof of achievability of the capacity region contains random coding analysis, in this section we shall improve this bound by using ensemble of codes built from piece-wise constant composition codewords, as will be described. The random constant composition codes can have better average performance than the random IID codes because they eliminate the existence of codewords with “bad type”. Hence better lower bounds on the error exponent

Figure 2.3: Static broadcast capacity region of a *modified* two language speaker channel. Regular broadcast capacity region indicated with dashed line.

can be achieved. The two bounds are known to be equal for the maximizing prior, but we are serving several channels simultaneously, and the maximizing prior may differ between the channels. In Appendix A we examine the differences in the error exponent at the different settings. Additionally such codes enable derivation (in a simpler manner) of upper bounds on the error exponent. Nevertheless, the random coding bounds for the IID case are valid for infinite and nondiscrete input and output alphabets, while the bounds to follow are valid only for finite size input and output alphabet.

As described, our code is constructed from codewords, each divided into several intervals, such that each interval has a given type. We have shown that these intervals are defined by the time each receiver quits. Due to the convexity of the mutual information, the symbols should be chosen according to an interval-dependent prior in the IID case and each interval should be chosen from

an interval-dependent type in the constant composition case. The latter case is discussed in this section.

It should be noted that the interval-wise construction of the code is indeed motivated by the desire to maximize the mutual information (and the convexity of the mutual information). There is no equivalent known result on the error exponent. However, as shown in Appendix A, a single-type (per interval) code is (exponentially) no worse than any other code. In any case, these are the codes we shall examine.

Our analysis will focus on the error probability of each of the receivers but not on other error events such as “one of the receivers had an error”. Simple bounds can be found for the latter case based on our analysis.

The gap between the average performance of the ensemble and the existence of a deterministic code can easily be bridged as in Theorem 2.1, given we have only finite number, d , of different channels. Hence there is a deterministic code with error probability not greater than d times the average error probability with respect to each channel.

2.4.1 Constant multitype codes for static broadcasting

We investigate codes that are *constant multitype*. These codes are made of codewords, such that each codeword is a concatenation of words from some constant composition codes. Denote by T_P^n the set of all vectors of length n , with empirical distribution P and by $T_V^n(\mathbf{x})$ the set of vectors of length n such that their empirical conditional distribution with respect to \mathbf{x} is V . We look at an ensemble of codes such that each code in it, \mathcal{C} , is a subset of the concatenation of L types:

$$\mathcal{C} \subset T_{P_1}^{l_1} \times T_{P_2}^{l_2} \times \cdots \times T_{P_L}^{l_L}.$$

The length of the codewords in this code is $N = \sum_i^L l_i$, and we shall define $\alpha_i = l_i/N$. We shall denote by \mathbf{P} such a multitype (both types and lengths). Hence, we may write $\mathcal{C} \subset T_{\mathbf{P}}$.

Similar to the definition of multitype, we define a corresponding conditional multitype, \mathbf{V} , to contain L conditional types V_1, \dots, V_L .

For a given DMC W we shall define $D(\mathbf{V}||W|\mathbf{P}) = \sum_i \alpha_i D(V_i||W|P_i)$. If $\mathbf{x} \in T_{\mathbf{P}}$, we shall denote by \mathbf{x}_i the i th segment of \mathbf{x} which is of length l_i and type P_i , e.g., $\mathbf{x}_i \in T_{P_i}$. We shall say that $\mathbf{y} \in T_{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{x})$, if for each i , $\mathbf{y}_i \in T_{V_i}(\mathbf{x}_i)$. In this case, we define² the (normalized) empirical mutual information between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} as

$$I(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{y}) = I(\mathbf{P}; \mathbf{V}) = \sum_i \alpha_i I(P_i; V_i). \quad (2.7)$$

The number of multitypes of length N with L intervals of lengths l_i , $N = \sum l_i$, over an alphabet of size $|\mathcal{X}|$ is upper bounded by

$$\prod_{i=1}^L \binom{l_i + |\mathcal{X}| - 1}{|\mathcal{X}| - 1} \leq \prod_{i=1}^L (l_i + 1)^{|\mathcal{X}| - 1} \leq \left(\frac{N}{L} + 1\right)^{L(|\mathcal{X}| - 1)}. \quad (2.8)$$

Similarly, the number of conditional multitypes given that the output alphabet size is $|\mathcal{Y}|$ (regardless of the input type) is bounded by

$$\left(\frac{N}{L} + 1\right)^{L(|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}| - 1)}. \quad (2.9)$$

The exact number of types can be easily found using simple combinatorics, but these bounds are sufficient since they are polynomial w.r.t. the length N , [17]. We may let L grow slowly with N . As long as $L = o(N)$ the number of multitypes is subexponential with N and it can be neglected when examining the error exponent.

2.4.2 Sphere-packing upper bound on the error exponent

In [19] there is a simple derivation of the sphere-packing lower bound on the error probability (upper bound on the error exponent) for constant composition codes. Given a code with codewords of type P and rate R , the error exponent is upper bounded for the channel W by

$$E_{sp}(R, W, P) = \min_{\substack{V \\ I(P; V) \leq R}} D(V||W|P).$$

A similar result for the multitype case is given in the following theorem.

²It should be noted that the mutual information between \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} could have been defined as $\sum_i \alpha_i I(P_i; \sum_j \alpha_j V_j)$, or even $I(\sum_i \alpha_i P_i; \sum_i \alpha_i V_i)$. Hence, the definition in (2.7) may be viewed as symbolic.

Theorem 2.2. *Let \mathcal{C} be any constant multitype code of length N , with $2^K = 2^{NR}$ codewords, such that each codeword is divided to L intervals of lengths $l_1 = \alpha_1 N, l_2 = \alpha_2 N, \dots, l_L = \alpha_L N$, each of type P_1, P_2, \dots, P_L , respectively. The error exponent when \mathcal{C} is used over a DMC W is upper bounded by*

$$E_{sp}(R, W, \mathbf{P}) = \min_{\substack{R_i \geq 0 \\ \sum \alpha_i R_i \leq R}} \sum \alpha_i E_{sp}(R_i, W, P_i). \quad (2.10)$$

Proof. Following the proof in [19] of the sphere-packing bound for constant composition codes, an error will occur with high probability (tends to 1) if the empirical channel instance has a mutual information less than the code rate, i.e., $NR \geq \sum_i l_i I(P_i; V_i) = NI(\mathbf{P}; \mathbf{V})$, where V_i is the empirical channel for the i th segment. Since $D(V||W|P)$ is the exponent of the probability of getting an empirical channel V given that the true channel is W and the codeword sent is of type P , we have

$$\begin{aligned} E_{sp}(R, W, \mathbf{P}) &= \min_{\substack{\mathbf{V} \\ I(\mathbf{P}; \mathbf{V}) \leq R}} D(\mathbf{V}||W|\mathbf{P}) \\ &= \min_{\substack{R_i \geq 0 \\ \sum \alpha_i R_i \leq R}} \min_{\substack{V_i \\ I(P_i; V_i) \leq R_i}} \sum \alpha_i D(V_i||W|P_i) \\ &= \min_{\substack{R_i \geq 0 \\ \sum \alpha_i R_i \leq R}} \sum \alpha_i E_{sp}(R_i, W, P_i). \end{aligned}$$

□

Since the number of multitypes is nonexponential with respect to N (equals the multiplicity of the number of types of each length l_i), any code has a multitype subcode with the same exponential size, and hence (almost) the same rate which proves the validity of the above sphere-packing bound for all codes. We should note that if the type is the same for all intervals, i.e., $P_i = P$, we obtain the adequate “regular” sphere-packing error exponent due to convexity.

2.4.3 Random coding lower bound on the error exponent

In this section we derive a lower bound on the error exponent by looking at the average performance of codes in a random ensemble. In the ensemble there is at least one code as good as the average.

The ensemble is defined by choosing each one of the $M = 2^{NR}$ codewords uniformly and independently from $T_{\mathbf{P}}$ (with repetitions). To simplify the derivation, we analyze the performance of the maximum mutual information (MMI) decoder. We prove that the MMI decoder has exponentially the same performance as the optimal decoder - the MAP decoder (which is the same as the ML decoder in our case).

For a received word, \mathbf{y} , the MMI decoder chooses the codeword, $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{C} \subset T_{\mathbf{P}}$ that maximizes the mutual information $I(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{y}) = I(\mathbf{P}; \mathbf{V})$, where \mathbf{V} is such that $\mathbf{y} \in T_{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{x})$.

Theorem 2.3. *The average error probability of a randomly chosen code from $T_{\mathbf{P}}$ with $2^K = 2^{NR}$ codewords of length N used over a DMC W with an MMI decoder, is upper bounded by*

$$\bar{P}_e \leq 2^{-N(E_r(R+\delta_N, W, \mathbf{P})-\delta_N)},$$

where

$$E_r(R, W, \mathbf{P}) = \min_{\mathbf{V}} D(\mathbf{V}||W|\mathbf{P}) + |I(\mathbf{P}; \mathbf{V}) - R|^+$$

and $\delta_N = \frac{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1}{NL^{-1}} \log(NL^{-1} + 1)$, where $|\mathcal{X}|$ and $|\mathcal{Y}|$ are the input and output alphabet sizes, respectively.

Proof. Since all codewords are of the same multitype and chosen independently, the average error probability equals the error probability given the codeword we sent is $\mathbf{x} \in T_{\mathbf{P}}$, then

$$\bar{P}_e = \sum_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{Y}^N} W(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x}) \Pr(\text{error}|\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \quad (2.11)$$

$$= \sum_{\mathbf{V}} W(\mathbf{y} \in T_{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{x})|\mathbf{x}) \Pr(\text{error}|\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y} \in T_{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{x})). \quad (2.12)$$

An error occurs if there is a codeword \mathbf{x}' such that $\mathbf{y} \in T_{\mathbf{V}'}(\mathbf{x}')$ and $I(\mathbf{P}; \mathbf{V}') \geq I(\mathbf{P}; \mathbf{V})$ (ties are taken as errors). Using the union bound over all possible $M - 1$ codewords, and bounding the probability by 1, leads to

$$\bar{P}_e \leq \sum_{\mathbf{V}} W(\mathbf{y} \in T_{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{x})|\mathbf{x}) \min \left\{ 1, (M - 1) \sum_{\substack{\mathbf{V}' \\ I(\mathbf{P}; \mathbf{V}') \geq I(\mathbf{P}; \mathbf{V})}} \Pr(\{\mathbf{x}' : \mathbf{y} \in T_{\mathbf{V}'}(\mathbf{x}')\}) \right\}. \quad (2.13)$$

Since \mathbf{x}' is uniformly chosen from $T_{\mathbf{P}}$

$$\Pr(\{\mathbf{x}' : \mathbf{y} \in T_{\mathbf{V}'}(\mathbf{x}')\}) \leq 2^{-NI(\mathbf{P};\mathbf{V}')}. \quad (2.14)$$

Likewise, for any \mathbf{x}

$$\Pr(\mathbf{y} \in T_{\mathbf{V}}(\mathbf{x})) \leq 2^{-N(D(\mathbf{V}||W|\mathbf{P}))}. \quad (2.15)$$

Now, bounding the summations in (2.13) by the number of terms times the greatest term and using (2.9) leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{P}_e &\leq (NL^{-1} + 1)^{L(|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1)} \\ &\quad \max_{\substack{\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{V}' \\ I(\mathbf{P};\mathbf{V}) \leq I(\mathbf{P};\mathbf{V}')}} 2^{-N(D(\mathbf{V}||W|\mathbf{P}))} \min\{1, (NL^{-1} + 1)^{L(|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1)} 2^{-N(I(\mathbf{P};\mathbf{V}')-R)}\}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.16)$$

Substituting $\mathbf{V}' = \mathbf{V}$ leads to an upper bound to the above, which completes the proof. \square

As in constant composition codes, there is a simple relation between the random coding error exponent and the sphere-packing error exponent:

$$\begin{aligned} E_r(R, W, \mathbf{P}) &= \min_{R'} \min_{\substack{\mathbf{V} \\ I(\mathbf{P};\mathbf{V}) \leq R'}} D(\mathbf{V}||W|\mathbf{P}) + |I(\mathbf{P}; \mathbf{V}) - R|^+ \\ &= \min_{R' \geq R} E_{sp}(R', W, \mathbf{P}) + R' - R. \end{aligned} \quad (2.17)$$

This relation between the random coding error exponent and the sphere-packing error exponent leads to the following corollary:

Corollary 2.4. *The random coding error exponent $E_r(R, W, \mathbf{P})$ is a tight bound for the average error probability over the random ensemble of constant multitype codes.*

Proof. Follow Lemma A.3. \square

The last corollary implies that the use of the MMI decoder instead of the optimal ML decoder does not cause exponential degradation in the expected error probability.

The existence of low rate codes with better error exponents than the ensemble's average can be achieved by expurgation [18]. Removing “bad” codes from the ensemble by posing some constraints on the relation between the codewords will yield better bounds on the remaining codes.

2.5 Discussion and Further Improvements

In defining the static broadcast channel capacity region, we utilized the possibility of transmitting the information at a higher rate if the receivers are not forced to be synchronously and simultaneously connected to the transmitter. Actually, the fact that various possible definitions of the capacity for the broadcast channel exist, depending on the subset of time the data is received has already been observed. For example, in [14], another definition of the achievable rates is presented which assumes an infinite reservoir of data (in opposite to the static broadcasting setting which assumes finite data).

Clearly the capacity region of the classical broadcast channel is contained in the static broadcasting capacity region. That is, if (R_0, R_1, R_2) is achievable under the classical broadcast channel setting, then $(R_0 + R_1, R_0 + R_2)$ is achievable in the static broadcasting setting.

A naive approach for utilizing the possibility to choose the receiving time interval is essentially queuing, i.e., the receivers wait in a queue for the transmitter to send them the information. In this case, the transmitter first transmits to one receiver, with effective rate equals to its capacity, then transmits to the second channel, and so on. Since the second receiver had to wait for the end of the transmission to the first receiver, the effective rates in this scenario for these two receivers are

$$R_1 = C_1 \quad \text{and} \quad R_2 = \frac{C_1 C_2}{C_1 + C_2}.$$

The static broadcasting approach leads to a higher rate as the receivers are not forced to be “on hold”. (Note, though, that there are channels, such as the “modified two language channel”, where, nevertheless, a receiver may need to be “on hold”).

2.5.1 Random starting point

In our setting we restricted the time intervals of all receivers to begin at the same time point. This means that “semi-synchronization” between the different receivers exists. They all start at the same time, however, the end time is not

common to all receivers. In this respect, our setting can be generalized to include an arbitrary initial point for each receiver. The rate, as before, will be defined as the number of information bits received divided by the time the receiver was “online”.

For example, if the starting points are known to be very far one from each other, the receiving intervals may not intersect, and so, the capacity of all channels can be achieved simultaneously.

A more interesting scenario is that the starting time of each receiver is not known (which is similar to having infinite receivers, each starts at a different point). We wish to allow the receivers to receive the data starting from any arbitrary point and obtain the information at the minimal possible time interval. This situation is interesting in practical scenarios. It is the case, for example, that occurs in reliable data transmission to many users using IP multicasting over the Internet, see [5] and references therein. In this case different receivers have different erasure probability, and the receivers have no synchronization between them. Due to the time invariant nature of this setting, codes whose structure depends on time are less likely to be used. Thus, it is expected that the formulas for the capacity region will be the same as (2.1), but with a constant input prior throughout the entire transmission, without the interval-wise structure.

2.5.2 Infinite set of channels

In our analysis in this chapter, we assumed the broadcast channel setting contains a finite set of channels. This was used in several places. In section 2.2 it was used to prove the existence of a code that is simultaneously good for all channels, to show that we have uniform convergence of the error probability over all channels and to justify the interval-wise construction of the code. In section 2.4 it was also used for assuming bounded output alphabet size and bounding the polynomial penalty on the number of intervals (in an extreme case of intervals of length 1, constant multitype means all codewords are the same).

There are many scenarios that lead to an infinite number of channels over a given discrete input. Some examples are:

- The collection of all channels with given input and output alphabet and positive capacity. In this case the infimum over the channels' capacity is zero which may lead to the use of infinite length codewords.
- Unbounded (even if discrete) output alphabet size. Each channel may have different output alphabet.
- One channel and infinite set of receivers. Each has a different effective rate in order to get different error probability.
- Each receiver starts at different time (as mentioned above).

In case of an infinite set of channels, the set of results we have shown is still valid for random codes. Although infinite length codes may be needed, the effective code length each channel/receiver uses is finite, albeit not necessarily bounded.

For the multitype analysis, the collection of possible channels should have a bounded output alphabet size (and not just finite for each channel) as there is a polynomial “penalty” in the error probability bound with respect to the output alphabet size.

Given the collection of channels $\{W_\theta : \theta \in \Theta\}$, we say that the infinite rate vector $\{R_\theta : \theta \in \Theta\}$ is achievable if a sequence of codes $\{\mathcal{C}_n\}$ exists such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Pr(\text{error}|\mathcal{C}_n, W_\theta, R_\theta) = 0$, where $\Pr(\text{error}|\mathcal{C}_n, W_\theta, R_\theta)$ is the error probability when using the code over the channel W_θ with effective rate of R_θ . Note that for a finite set of channels, this definition of achievability implies the existence of a good deterministic code and uniform convergence of the error probability. For the infinite collection of channels some nuances exist, such as “Do we have uniform convergence of the above error probability?” For the convergence to the closure of all achievable rates one may ask whether we achieve points $R_\theta - \epsilon$ for all $\theta \in \Theta$, or $R_\theta(1 - \epsilon)$. The difference is that in the first definition, the code does not need to handle channels with capacity less than ϵ . In [27] there is a good survey of the difference between random and deterministic codes, uniform convergence vs. nonuniform (strong vs. weak convergence) etc.

The case of infinite channels may lead to use an unbounded number of different priors in (2.1). For example, assume the collection of all possible Z-channels with positive capacity: $\{W_\theta(0|0) = 1, W_\theta(0|1) = \theta\}$, $\theta \in [0, 1)$. Each channel has a different capacity and different capacity achieving prior, $e^{-1} < P(X = 1) \leq \frac{1}{2}$, see [33]. Hence some of the points in the capacity region can be achieved by codes for which the prior of each symbol is different. Also note that the code length in this case is infinite in order to handle channels with arbitrary small capacity. This may cause a problem in the multitype ensemble, since the number of intervals, and hence, the number of different types/priors are limited. But the results are still valid, since any point in the capacity region can be reached arbitrarily closely by unbounded increasing of the number of intervals L as K (and N) are increased. As noted previously, L can be $o(K)$.

Part of the solutions to the problem related to infinitely many channels can be found in works related to universal decoding, [27] and references therein. The existence of a good code for the entire collection of discrete memoryless channels with common input and output alphabets and bounded (from below) capacity is shown in [18]. Using the results on periodic codes in Chapter 6, we can translate a problem of infinite many channels with positive, but possibly infinitely small capacity, to the problem that we have a bounded away from zero capacity (minimum quality criterion), but with unbounded output alphabet size.

2.5.3 Universal coding

The codes we have suggested are block codes, with a block length that fits the time needed to allow the last receiver enough data to decode the information. In some situations, the transmitter may be unaware of the various channels to which it broadcasts. In this case, we have to design a code that translates the information bits into, possibly, infinite transmission.

The previous situation may occur when we use the broadcast channel to model universal communication to an unknown channel. If the receiver can relay to the transmitter that it received the data correctly, our static broadcast scenario leads to a communication solution over the unknown (or compound) channel that

reliably works at a higher rate than that guaranteed by the compound channel capacity, but with feedback.

When the channel is not known at the receiver, it can use universal decoding [19, 27]. Universal decoding may put some constraints on the code design, and may complicate the receiver, but is possible without increasing the rate (and even without affecting the error probability in an exponential manner). Universal decoding together with possible infinite transmission can be used as a complete solution for universal communication. This will be dealt with in depth in the next chapter.

Chapter 3

Universal Communication Using Static Broadcasting

The static broadcasting method described in Chapter 2 can be used for communicating over an unknown channel, i.e., for universal communication. The existence of a universal *decoder*, e.g., an MMI decoder, was demonstrated in section 2.4. In this chapter we extend the scope of universality to the encoder and to the entire communication scheme.

The communication method that will be described does not make an explicit attempt to estimate the real underlying channel, but, of course, the expected performance, both effective rate and error probability, depends on the actual channel.

When using universal decoding it seems that universal communication is feasible. Indeed, using an MMI decoder, virtually the same performance¹ may be achieved as with one that knows the channel and uses an ML decoder. However, the lack of information about channel statistics at the encoder leads to two problems. The first is that the code cannot be tuned to the specific channel, e.g., the suitable input prior that achieves the channel's capacity or the best error probability for a given rate. The second problem is the rate problem. The encoder does not know at which rate to transmit. Although the universal decoder attains the same performance as a decoder that knows the channel, this is useless at rates above capacity [4, 22], even if feedback exists [20].

¹The achievable rate is the same, and there is no exponential degradation in the error probability for rates above the critical rate.

The first problem may be solved by an encoder that knows which prior to use, e.g., it received information on the channel via feedback. The second problem, of working at a correct (below capacity) rate, can be solved through a settings similar to that of the static broadcasting.

At the basis of our scheme to follow stands a sequential use of *universal erasure decoding*. Knowledge of the working rate is essential in the basic universal erasure decoding, but in our scenario we lack this knowledge. Hence, we replace the rate with the effective rate at each time point.

3.1 Sequential Decoding

All bounds shown in Chapter 2 examine the performance of some prefix of the code for each channel. Hence the analysis was of block-to-block codes. But the static broadcasting concept and its code construction can be used with sequential decision making in the decoder to improve the error probability. If the channel law is known to the decoder, at any point during the reception, an ML decoder, equivalent to MAP decoder, knows the probability that it makes an error in its decoding. Hence it may stay “tuned” for a longer period in order to achieve a desired error probability, i.e., instead of predetermining the observation length of each receiver, a sequential decoding can be used. This leads to random observation time, but significantly improves the error probability compared to the previous scenario with the same (average) observation time.

For example, assume an erasure channel with erasure probability δ . By using infinite length random (possibly linear) code to transmit K bits, the receiver may stay tuned until it successfully decodes the message with zero error probability. On average, the receiver should have, as will be shown later, about $K+2$ unerased symbols in order to decode the message. Hence, it should listen, on average, for a period of $(K+2)/(1-\delta)$ which leads to the effective rate $(1-\delta)K/(K+2)$. The receiver may work at a rate close to the capacity $C = 1 - \delta$, for large K , with error probability equals *zero*.

As can be seen from the above example, the same scheme can be applied when both the encoder and the decoder do not know in advance the channel’s

erasure probability, δ . The example not only demonstrates that sequential decoding can improve error probability, but even illustrates its ability to be a basis for a communication scheme in which the needed code length, and hence the working rate, are not known in advance. Hence, a sequential decoder may enable communication with a good effective working rate in scenarios where the channel is unknown.

Below is a detailed analysis of sequential decoding for a binary erasure channel with unknown erasure probability. The superb results achieved for this case, as will be demonstrated, are since there is a most powerful uniform decoder for this ensemble of channels and its decoding error probability is zero.

3.1.1 The binary erasure channel

All binary erasure channels have the same MAP/ML decoder. This decoder decodes a codeword that matches all unerased bits received (hopefully only one such codeword exists). Hence, a decoder for such a channel may be used without knowing the accurate erasure probability, $\epsilon < 1$, as long as the code rate is at most $1 - \epsilon$. In the scope of static broadcasting, the encoder may send infinite length codewords, and each receiver may stop receiving once the effective rate is less than the capacity dictated by the effective erasure probability.

But the erasure channel also has a simple and optimal sequential decoder: Receive symbols sequentially until just one codeword (the correct one) fits all unerased bits received. Hence zero error probability is achieved².

Once the above decoder is used, we may analyze some codes and see their performance. We shall look at both (infinite) random linear codes and (infinite) random codes, where in the latter each symbol is chosen uniformly and independently. Since these code ensembles have no time-dependent structure, the erasure patterns are not important, only the number of unerased bits. If the code has $M = 2^K$ codewords, clearly no one would expect to decode a word, on average, in less than K unerased received bits. Hence the following analysis will look for

²In the sequel, a universal sequential decoder based on an MMI decoder will be used. This decoder does not yield zero error probability even if the underlying channel is an erasure channel, see example in Appendix A.

the average of unerased bits above K needed to correctly decode the message.

Random Linear Code

We assume a random linear code which contains $M = 2^K$ codewords of infinite length. The random linear code is created by randomly choosing, for each time slot, a linear functional which produces a bit by adding (mod 2) a subset of the K information bits (this subset defines the functional) [62, 68, 70]. There are several works that focus on finding such (random) linear codes that are both easy to encode and to decode, e.g., [3].

Since we are looking at the erasure channel, it is possible to decode when the set of functionals that fit the unerased bits is solvable, i.e., the set of linear functionals has full rank, K .

We should note that while each possible linear code may have a different decoding length, given the location of the erased bits, it is possible to determine whether it can be decoded. This is not the case in the total random code described in the next section.

Assuming that at time t we have a collection of functionals (fitting the unerased received bits) with rank l . What is the probability that the next unerased bit will increase the rank to $l + 1$? There are 2^K different functionals, and only 2^l are dependent on the received functionals. Hence this probability is $1 - 2^{l-K}$. Due to the independency of the events, on average one needs

$$\frac{1}{1 - 2^{l-K}} = \frac{2^K}{2^K - 2^l} \quad (3.1)$$

unerased symbols to get from rank l to rank $l + 1$. Thus, the average number of unerased symbols needed, $\bar{L}_{\text{lnr}}(K)$, to get from rank 0 to rank K is

$$\bar{L}_{\text{lnr}}(K) = \sum_{l=0}^{K-1} \frac{2^K}{2^K - 2^l}. \quad (3.2)$$

$\bar{L}_{\text{lnr}}(K) - K$ increases monotonically, but is bounded by 2. Actually a refined calculation leads to

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \bar{L}_{\text{lnr}}(K) - K = 1.6067... \quad (3.3)$$

Random Symbols Code

In random symbols code, each bit in each codeword is chosen independently and uniformly. Again, the code and channel are time invariant. Consequently we can look only at unerased time slots.

Unlike the case of linear codes, in this situation a codeword can be decoded when fewer than K unerased bits are received (which, of course, does not apply for the average over the codewords). For example, there is a (small) positive probability that only a single codeword will begin with ‘1’, and the rest will begin with ‘0’. In this case, we can decode this unique codeword from a single bit.

The probability that at least one of the $M - 1$ codewords that were not sent will have the received (unerased) l bits that the sent codeword has is

$$\Pr(l \text{ is not enough}) = 1 - (1 - 2^{-l})^{M-1}. \quad (3.4)$$

Hence, we have

$$\bar{L}_{\text{IID}}(K) = \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} 1 - (1 - 2^{-l})^{2^K - 1}. \quad (3.5)$$

Again, $\bar{L}_{\text{IID}}(K) - K$ is bounded, and we have

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \bar{L}_{\text{IID}}(K) - K = 1.3327... \quad (3.6)$$

Thus, in this scenario, using the sequential decoder, and when K is large enough

$$R_{\text{seq}} \geq \frac{1 - \varepsilon}{1 + 1.3328K^{-1}}. \quad (3.7)$$

The random symbols code has a lower redundancy than the random linear code. For low rates, linear codes may demonstrate better performance than totally random codes, .e.g., [6], but the analysis above is for near capacity rates.

There are almost no maximum distance separable (MDS) [50] binary linear codes³. Nevertheless, the results above demonstrate that both linear and IID random codes are, on the average, not far from optimal MDS. We should note

³The only binary linear MDS codes are the whole space codes (rate 1), the even weight codes (very high rate - $\frac{K}{K+1}$) and repetition codes (very low rate - only 2 codewords).

that unlike the results on the error probability and minimum distance of random linear codes [69], the almost-MDS property above is averaged over all erasure patterns and not just over the ensemble.

Nonbinary Erasure Channels

A similar analysis can be made for nonbinary erasure channels. For example assume an erasure channel with q input symbols. Assuming there is a field of size q , similarly to equation (3.2), for a random linear code with q^K codewords, we have

$$\bar{L}_{\text{nr}}(K) = \sum_{l=0}^{K-1} \frac{q^K}{q^K - q^l}. \quad (3.8)$$

For example, assume $q = 256$ (using $\text{GF}(2^8)$ field), a random linear code will have expected symbols redundancy of

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \bar{L}_{\text{nr}}(K) - K = 0.0039\dots \quad (3.9)$$

Even if we scale to bits, i.e., multiplying by $\log_2 q$, the redundancy is much smaller than in the binary case. Note that if only a small fraction of the equations are over the big field, e.g., $\text{GF}(256)$, and the rest are over the small one, e.g., $\text{GF}(2)$, the expected redundancy will be small as if all equation were over the big field. This can be useful in practical scenarios such as the Internet, where the symbols are big (packets) and the channel is, basically, an erasure channel.

A Note on ARQ

When the channel's erasure probability, ε , is known, an ARQ scheme can be used with code length $N = \frac{K+x}{1-\varepsilon}$ for some x . If the probability of declaring erasure-decoding is P_E , then $R = \frac{K(1-\varepsilon)}{K+x} \frac{1}{1-P_E}$. A simple bound for P_E is

$$P_E \geq \Pr(\text{no more than } K \text{ unerased bits}) \Pr(K \text{ bits are insufficient to decode}).$$

The right argument is larger than $1/4$ for both the linear and IID cases. On average, the number of unerased bits is $K + x$ with variance $\varepsilon(K + x)$ (ignoring integer problems). Using the law of large numbers, to have $P_E \rightarrow 0$, x should increase faster than \sqrt{K} . Hence, instead of rate loss of the order of $\frac{1}{K}$ (with a

very small constant) in sequential decoding, the ARQ scheme leads to a rate loss of (at least) the order of $\frac{1}{\sqrt{K}}$.

3.2 Universal Communication - Problem Description

Using the concept of static broadcasting, we now demonstrate the existence of a communication scheme that does not know the channel law, but nevertheless enables reliable communication between encoder and decoder. This is the essence of the following theorem

Theorem 3.1. *Consider a discrete memoryless channel with input alphabet \mathcal{X} and unknown channel law. For any prior P over the input alphabet \mathcal{X} and for any K , there is an encoder with $M = 2^K$ codewords, and a decoding scheme that depends only on \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} such that*

- *The decoding error probability is uniformly bounded over all possible channels.*
- *The average decoding length for each channel W , $\bar{N}(W)$ is finite if $I(P; W) > 0$.*
- *The effective working rate tends to $I(P; W)$ as K grows, i.e.,*

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{K}{\bar{N}(W)} = I(P; W).$$

Note that the theorem claims for uniform convergence of the error probability over the collection of channels as K grows. Hence, for any desired error probability, there is a (random) code that for any possible actual channel will have a decoding error with probability lower than desired. We are not addressing the problem of “better channels should have better error performance”, rather we claim “all channels are good enough (though some will take longer to decode)”.

The proof for this theorem is provided in Section 3.3. It is a constructive proof based on building a random code with a universal sequential decoder that achieves what is claimed in the theorem.

Appendix B contains another encoding scheme that is based on *almost* constant composition codes, which has better error performance, as expected.

3.3 Universal Sequential Decoder

In this section we examine a universal sequential decoder that operates on an infinite length code. This will lead to the proof of Theorem 3.1.

We assume an IID random code. The code contains $M = 2^K$ infinite length codewords $\mathcal{C} = \{\mathbf{x}_i : i = 1 \dots M\} \subset \mathcal{X}^\infty$. Each symbol of each codeword is chosen independently with prior P over the finite set \mathcal{X} .

The decoder, after receiving n -length prefix of the channel's output, \mathbf{y} , works with an effective rate

$$R_n = \frac{\log M}{n} = \frac{K}{n} \quad (3.10)$$

and uses the following decoding rule $\phi_n(\mathbf{y})$: For $\tilde{R}_n \geq R'_n$

$$\phi_n(\mathbf{y}) = \begin{cases} i & \text{if } I_n(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{y}) \geq \tilde{R}_n \text{ and } \forall j \neq i \quad I_n(\mathbf{x}_j; \mathbf{y}) < R'_n \\ 0 & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (3.11)$$

where 0 stands for erasure decoding (detected error), and I_n stands for the empirical mutual information of the sequences n -length prefixes (this subscript will be omitted in the sequel). The decoder does not make any use of the channel law, and hence, it is a universal decoder. In addition to the detected error, the decoder may err and decode $j \neq i$. In this case, we say that an undetected error occurred. If erasure occurred, the decoder receives another symbol and repeats the above with $n + 1$.

We should demonstrate the existence of sequences \tilde{R}_n and R'_n that ensures low error probability and a good effective rate. The effective rate is $R = \frac{\log M}{N}$, where N is the stopping time of the decoding:

$$N = \min\{n : \phi_n(\mathbf{y}) \neq 0\}, \quad (3.12)$$

i.e., N is the random variable that represents how long the receiver should stay tuned until decoding (with or without an undetected error). Given N , erasure occurred for all $n < N$, hence

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N} &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \Pr(N = n) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \Pr(N \geq n) = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \Pr(N > n) \\ &\leq 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \Pr(\phi_n(\mathbf{y}) = 0). \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

The last inequality is not equality as it is possible to have $\phi_{n'}(\mathbf{y}) = 0$ even if $\phi_n(\mathbf{y}) \neq 0$ for $n' > n$.

In the sequel we shall assume that the message sent was i . However, as the code is random, the probability of the error events are not dependent on it, and i will not be explicitly stated. The error event (detected or undetected) is contained in $A_n \cup B_n$ where

$$A_n = \{ I(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{y}) < \tilde{R}_n \} \quad (3.14)$$

$$B_n = \{ I(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{y}) \geq \tilde{R}_n \text{ and } \exists j \neq i, I(\mathbf{x}_j; \mathbf{y}) \geq R'_n \}. \quad (3.15)$$

The probability of the event in (3.14) can be bounded by

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(A_n) &\leq \sum_{\substack{V, Q \\ I(Q; V) < \tilde{R}_n}} \exp_2 \{ -n [D(V \| W | Q) + D(Q \| P)] \} \quad (3.16) \\ &\leq \max_{\substack{V, Q \\ I(Q; V) < \tilde{R}_n}} (n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1} \exp_2 \{ -n [D(V \| W | Q) + D(Q \| P)] \}, \end{aligned}$$

where W is the underlying actual channel law and $(n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1}$ is an upper bound to $\binom{n+|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1}{n}$, which is the number of possible joint types of input and output sequences of length n .

The probability of the event in (3.15) can be bounded by

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(B_n) &\leq \sum_{\substack{V, Q: I(Q; V) \geq \tilde{R}_n \\ V', Q': I(Q'; V') \geq R'_n \\ QV = Q'V'}} \exp_2 \{ -n [D(V \| W | Q) + D(Q \| P) + |I(V'; Q') + D(Q' \| P) - R_n|^+] \} \quad (3.17) \\ &\leq \max_{\substack{V, Q: I(Q; V) \geq \tilde{R}_n \\ V', Q': I(Q'; V') \geq R'_n \\ QV = Q'V'}} (n+1)^{2|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-2} \\ &\quad \exp_2 \{ -n [D(V \| W | Q) + D(Q \| P) + |I(V'; Q') + D(Q' \| P) - R_n|^+] \}. \end{aligned}$$

A simpler bound (which is good for rates near $I(P; W)$) will be

$$\Pr(B_n) \leq \Pr(\exists j \neq i, I(\mathbf{x}_j; \mathbf{y}) \geq R'_n) \leq (n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1} \exp_2 \{ -n(R'_n - R_n) \} \quad (3.18)$$

Define the event U_n

$$U_n = \{ I(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{y}) < R'_n \text{ and } \exists j \neq i, I(\mathbf{x}_j; \mathbf{y}) \geq \tilde{R}_n \}. \quad (3.19)$$

U_n contains the event of an undetected error. Similarly to (3.15) and (3.17), we have

$$\Pr(U_n) \leq \max_{\substack{V, Q: I(Q; V) \leq R'_n \\ V', Q': I(Q'; V') \geq \tilde{R}_n \\ QV = Q'V'}} (n+1)^{2|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-2} \exp_2\{-n[D(V||W|Q) + D(Q||P) + |I(V'; Q') + D(Q' || P) - R_n|^+]\}. \quad (3.20)$$

Furthermore, as in (3.18), a simple bound to the undetected error probability is

$$\Pr(U_n) \leq \Pr(\exists j \neq i, I(\mathbf{x}_j; \mathbf{y}) \geq \tilde{R}_n) \leq (n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1} \exp_2\{-n(\tilde{R}_n - R_n)\}. \quad (3.21)$$

It is obvious that there is no point in trying to decode if $R_n > \log |\mathcal{X}|$. Indeed, we can see that no channel V' can comply with the conditions in (3.20) if $\tilde{R}_n > \log |\mathcal{X}|$. Hence

$$\Pr(U_n) = 0 \quad \text{if } \tilde{R}_n > \log |\mathcal{X}|. \quad (3.22)$$

If work at rates close to $I(P; W)$ and small undetected error probability are desired, we use

$$\tilde{R}_n = R_n + (|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}| + \mu) \frac{\log(n+1)}{n} \quad (3.23)$$

for some $\mu > 0$. Note that the decoder is aware of the channel's output alphabet. With this setting, the probability of error throughout the transmission, regardless the channel law, can be bounded using (3.21), (3.22) and (3.23)

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{error}) &\leq \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \Pr(U_n) \\ &\leq \sum_{n=\lceil K/\log |\mathcal{X}| \rceil}^{\infty} (n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1} \exp_2\{-n(\tilde{R}_n - R_n)\} \\ &= \sum_{n=\lceil K/\log |\mathcal{X}| \rceil}^{\infty} (n+1)^{-(\mu+1)} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\mu} (K/\log |\mathcal{X}|)^{-\mu}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

Thus, for any desired error probability, we can either use large enough code (K large enough) or use μ large enough to achieve it⁴. Setting

$$R'_n = \tilde{R}_n = R_n + (|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}| + \mu) \frac{\log(n+1)}{n}, \quad (3.25)$$

⁴For example, for binary input channel, $|\mathcal{X}| = 2$, and desired error probability of 10^{-6} , code with 2^K codewords, $K = 50$, and $\mu = 4$ will do, regardless of the underlying actual channel.

the average reception length, $\bar{N}(W)$, which depends on the actual channel, can be bounded, for any $N_0(W) > \lceil K/\log |\mathcal{X}| \rceil$, using (3.13), by

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N}(W) &\leq 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \Pr(A_n(W) \cup B_n(W)) \\ &\leq N_0(W) + \sum_{n=N_0(W)}^{\infty} \Pr(A_n(W)) + \Pr(B_n(W)) \\ &\leq N_0(W) + 1 + \sum_{n=N_0(W)}^{\infty} \Pr(A_n(W)), \end{aligned} \quad (3.26)$$

where the second inequality is attained by bounding $\sum \Pr(B_n)$ with 1 for large enough K , similarly to (3.24). For channels with positive mutual information⁵ $\Pr(A_n)$ in (3.16) decays exponentially (or even faster) to 0 for large enough n since \tilde{R}_n goes to 0 as n increases. Consequently, for *any* channel W such that $I(P; W) > 0$, we have a finite average decoding length, $\bar{N}(W) < \infty$. This implies that the probability that the decoding process will stop is 1.

We shall now make a slightly more accurate calculation of the expected observation length, $\bar{N}(W)$. Define

$$F(R, W, P) = \min_{\substack{V, Q \\ I(Q; V) < R}} D(V||W|Q) + D(Q||P). \quad (3.27)$$

Substituting in equation (3.16) yields

$$\Pr(A_n(W)) \leq (n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1} \exp_2\{-nF(\tilde{R}_n, W, P)\}. \quad (3.28)$$

For any $r > 0$, define $N_0(W) = \lceil \frac{K}{I(P; W) - 2r} \rceil$. For large enough K (and fixed μ), if $n > N_0(W)$ then $\tilde{R}_n < I(P; W) - r$. $F(R, W, P)$ decreases with respect to R , and it is positive iff $R < I(P; W)$. Define $\delta(r) = F(I(P; W) - r, W, P)$, then $\delta(r) > 0$ for $r > 0$. Using equation (3.26) leads to

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{N}(W)}{K} &\leq \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_0(W) + 1 + \sum_{n=N_0(W)}^{\infty} (n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1} \exp_2\{-n\delta(r)\}}{K} \\ &= \lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N_0(W)}{K} \\ &= \frac{1}{I(P; W) - 2r}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.29)$$

⁵Note that if the prior P is positive for all symbols then $I(P; W) = 0$ iff $C(W) = 0$.

where the first equality holds since $N_0(W)$ goes to infinity as K goes to infinity. As this is true for any $r > 0$, and the expected decoding rate should be at least $I(P; W)$, the limit is

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{K}{\bar{N}(W)} = I(P; W).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 3.1. \square

3.4 Summary

We have demonstrated the existence of a communication scheme that can be used over an unknown channel to reliably transmit a finite amount of data, without the need for some “minimum quality” of the underlying channels. The scheme’s rate approaches the mutual information induced by the underlying actual channel and the used prior, P , as the message size grows.

The core of our sequential decoder is the universal erasure decoder in (3.11). This universal erasure decoder is based on the universal erasure decoder presented in [19]:

$$\phi(\mathbf{y}) = \begin{cases} i & \text{if } I(\mathbf{x}_i; \mathbf{y}) \geq \tilde{R} + \lambda |I(\mathbf{x}_j; \mathbf{y}) - R|^+ \text{ for } j \neq i \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3.30)$$

for any $\lambda > 0$ and $\tilde{R} > R$. Since we are focused on near capacity rates, one of the modifications we made is taking $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$.

Although focused on high rates, i.e., rates close to the mutual information induced by the code’s prior, one may be interested in trading rate for error probability. The choices we have made for \tilde{R}_n and R'_n are focused on the high rate region. Choosing \tilde{R}_n or both \tilde{R}_n and R'_n larger than R_n by bigger terms than used in our analysis will lead to better error performance at the expense of rate, which indicate a tradeoff between decoding rate and decoding error probability. Note that in order to ensure that we have finite decoding for *all* possible channels with positive capacity, both \tilde{R}_n and R'_n should tend to zero as n goes to infinity.

Also, as known, random constant composition codes may show better performance than IID codes, but it is not possible to have a sequential code such that each prefix of it is a (strict) constant composition code. A definition and analysis

of *almost* constant composition codes, used with the universal sequential decoder we suggested in this chapter, appears in Appendix B.

Erasure decoder, which is the basis for the sequential scheme, can be significantly simpler when the underlying channel is erasure channel. For these specific channels, a more detailed analysis was made and superb performance were shown.

To achieve repeatable communication, one may add some form of feedback from the decoder to the encoder to enable progression to the next block of information.

Chapter 4

Universal Communication - The Rate Problem

An encoder wanting to transmit over a channel at the maximum possible rate can design a code for that task knowing only that rate (the channel capacity) and the optimal input symbol distribution that attains this capacity but does not have to know the complete channel probability distribution. Unfortunately if the channel is unknown, both its capacity and its capacity achieving prior are unknown. Nevertheless, the transmitter may consider a worst-case approach over the class of possible channels and design its scheme to attain the “compound channel capacity” $\max_P \inf_W I(P; W)$ [19]. This worst-case approach has two drawbacks. First, the operating rate may be much lower than the actual channel capacity. Second, in many cases the compound capacity is zero, making the worst-case approach useless. Another possible approach introduced in the previous chapters is to send a block of data via random code and rely on universal sequential detection at the decoder. If feedback exists, the encoder learns the effective rate of its transmission. If feedback does not exist, the encoder will remain ignorant of the rate, but according to the results above on static broadcasting, the one-shot communication of a fixed block of data can be done at the optimal rate.

This chapter focuses on the rate problem, i.e., how to communicate when the rate is unknown. We assume a given prior and so the optimal rate we wish to achieve is the mutual information induced by this prior. The discussion on how to choose a universal prior is done in Chapter 5.

The rate R of any communication scheme, measured say, in bits per unit time, is the number of information bits, divided by the (average) time needed to transmit them. In the common approach these three variables - rate, time and amount of information - are known to all sides of the communication system, and their value is constrained so that reliable communication can be maintained. In the previous chapters we considered the simple point-to-point communication channel whose mutual information $I(P; W)$ is not known in advance, and hence the rate that satisfies the constraint $R < I(P; W)$ cannot be predetermined. Yet, we demonstrated a reliable communication scheme in which the encoder remained ignorant about the working rate. In this chapter we consider additional communication settings in which not only the rate is unknown, but also the value or the constraints on other variables, such as the *amount* of side information, are not known in advance.

Specifically, in this chapter we consider the following settings. First, we discuss the case where the amount of information to be transmitted over an unknown channel is unknown in advance. Then we consider a Slepian-Wolf setting, where the amount of side information at the receiver is unknown in advance. Another scenario is the case of side information at the encoder that affects the chosen prior and hence the transmission rate. In all of these schemes the key component is a universal sequential decoder that follows the construction of the previous chapter. We conclude the chapter by combining it all and demonstrating a fully universal one-shot communication system, which although designed with almost no prior knowledge, works reliably at the optimal parameter values.

4.1 Transmitting an Unknown Amount of Data over an Unknown Channel

There are scenarios in which the amount of data a transmitter will send is unknown in advance. For example, a deep-space mission is planned to transmit back to earth all the knowledge of a newly discovered civilization. In this case the amount of information is probably finite, but unknown, and not even bounded in advance. Another example is when we want to transmit a sequence from a

source, but want to compress it first. The compressed size might be unknown in advance as it may depend on the actual source sequence.

The construction of the communication scheme for this scenario is quite straightforward. Assume that at least K_0 bits need to be transmitted. For each $K > K_0$ there is a code of the type described in Section 3.3 that assigns for each message of length K a codeword that can be as large as desired. If the message to be transmitted is of length K_m , the K_m th code is used, and the appropriate codeword from it is transmitted. For each code associated with the various message lengths, we use the sequential decoder described in (3.11). For each received symbol the sequential decoder either stays undecided and gets the next symbol or makes a decision and stops.

In the proposed communication scheme we apply these sequential decoders simultaneously, i.e., for each received symbol, all the decoders attempt to decode, and the first decoder that decides, its decision is the decoded message. Clearly, if the K th decoder decides, the decoded message is of length K . If two or more decoders decide simultaneously, we arbitrarily choose one of them, and we assume that an error occurred.

Let us analyze the error probability of this scheme. If the correct decoder makes the decision, i.e., the decoded message has the correct length, we may have an error, but the probability of this error can be made as small as desired, as shown in the previous chapter. However, in this scheme there is another error event that the wrong decoder makes the decision, i.e., the decoded message and the correct message have different lengths. We show now that the probability of this event can also be made as small as desired.

Assuming that the real message sent was of length K_m bits. Denote by $\Pr(\text{length error}, K, n)$ the probability that the K th decoder, where $K \neq K_m$, will make a decision after receiving n symbols. Similarly to (3.18) we can bound this probability by

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{length error}, K, n) &\leq \Pr(\exists i \in \{1, \dots, 2^K\}, I_n(\mathbf{x}_K(i); \mathbf{y}) \geq R'_n(K)) \\ &\leq (n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|} \exp_2\{-n(R'_n(K) - R_n(K))\}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

where \mathbf{y} is the received sequence of length n , $R_n(K) = K/n$, $\mathbf{x}_K(i)$ is the i th codeword of the K th code, and $R'_n(K) > R_n(K)$ is the R'_n parameter of the K th decoder defined in Section 3.3.

Setting

$$R'_n(K) = R_n(K) + (|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}| + \mu) \frac{\log(n+1)}{n}$$

and the fact that no decoding attempt is done by the K th decoder as long as $R'_n(K) > \log |\mathcal{X}|$, we can bound the probability of decoding a message of wrong length by

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{length error}) &\leq \sum_{K \geq K_0} \sum_{n > 0} \Pr(\text{length error}, K, n) \\ &\leq \sum_{K \geq K_0} \sum_{n > \lceil K/\log |\mathcal{X}| \rceil} (n+1)^{-(\mu+1)} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{\mu} \sum_{K \geq K_0} (K/\log |\mathcal{X}|)^{-\mu} \\ &< \frac{(K_0/\log |\mathcal{X}|)^{-\mu+1}}{\mu(\mu-1) \log |\mathcal{X}|}. \end{aligned}$$

As in (3.24), with large enough K_0 , and/or large enough μ , the above error probability can be as small as desired.

Note that even if the underlining channel is clean, the event of decoding a message with a wrong length has a nonzero probability. For example, the above error event includes the event that a codeword for the K th code will have the same, long enough, prefix as the sent codeword that belongs to K_m th code for $K_m > K$.

In the case of clean channel, the scheme above can be considered as universal source code for the integers [24] where a small error probability is allowed. Since the message length can be unbounded, we can attach to each integer, N , a message of length $\lfloor \log_2 N \rfloor$, that represents its binary expansion (without its most significant bit, which equals 1). Following the results above, the decoder can decode the integer (the message) with as small as desired error probability after receiving $\log_2 N$ bits plus negligible terms. This example demonstrates that the uncertainty in the message length can be resolved. This was well known for universal source coding where this uncertainty led to negligible addition in

the code length. This section showed that in our setting, there exists a similar phenomena.

An interesting consequence of the scheme above is the ability to universally transmit a block source that can be compressed to an unknown size over an unknown channel at the optimal rate. Specifically, let S be a discrete source over alphabet \mathcal{S} , with (unknown) entropy, $H(S)$. We want to design a communication scheme that transmits a block of size K of this source over an unknown DMC, W . The encoder may use a universal source code to compress the source, with a restriction of, say, a minimal size of $K_0 = \log K$ bits¹. Then, the above scheme can be used, with possible message size between $\log K$ and $\lceil K \log |\mathcal{S}| \rceil + 1$. For any desired $\epsilon > 0$ there exists K large enough that will guarantee that the decoding error probability will be less than ϵ for any possible channel. Assuming the code uses prior P , the average decoding length satisfies

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{K}{\bar{N}} = \frac{H(S)}{I(P; W)}. \quad (4.2)$$

Note that the encoder, regardless of the compressed size, attaches to each information message an infinite codeword (chosen randomly IID with prior P). Hence, the source coding can be skipped at the encoder and be effectively utilized only at the decoder. Moreover, the (universal) source code, can be *any* one-to-one function from a source sequence to sequence of bits:

$$g : \mathcal{S}^K \rightarrow \bigcup_{n \geq \log K} \{0, 1\}^n.$$

This flexibility enables, for example, improvement of the decoder and, in turn, improvement of the transmission rate without changing the encoder. Returning to our deep-space mission example - if the source is a picture taken by the starship, the decoder on earth can utilize new image compression techniques that were not available when the starship was built and as a result achieve greater communication rate.

¹Instead of $\log K$, K_0 may be any monotonic, unbounded function of K as long as $K_0 = o(K)$.

4.2 Universal Slepian-Wolf - Source Broadcasting to Heterogeneous Receivers

The Slepian-Wolf scheme [75] for source coding with side information at the receiver presented the following surprising result. A source X can be compressed to $R = H(X|Y)$ bits per symbol, where Y is the side information, although only the receiver knows Y . However, the Slepian-Wolf scheme necessitates knowledge of the optimal required rate. In this section we consider a situation where this rate is not known, possibly because the source is broadcasted to many heterogeneous receivers. The results in this section are based on the static broadcasting scheme and the universal sequential decoder presented in previous chapters and in [71, 72].

Before presenting our results, let us briefly recall the main idea in the Slepian-Wolf scheme. The scheme is based on the concept of random binning. A random index in the range $\{1, \dots, 2^{n(H(X|Y)+\epsilon)}\}$, where $\epsilon > 0$, is chosen to represent each possible source block of length n where each index value represents a bin. Now, many source sequences may correspond to the same bin. It turns out that with high probability (for large enough n) only one sequence at each bin is jointly typical with the side information sequence, with respect to the joint distribution of (X, Y) . Thus, the receiver can reconstruct the source sequence given the bin's index as it has the side information. The Slepian-Wolf scheme is universal in the sense that the sender source code is independent of the specific side information sequence y_1^n . The code is also independent of the specific statistical distribution of (X, Y) . However, as mentioned above, the sender *must* know the rate $R = H(X|Y)$ that is necessary for the receiver, who has the side information and knows the statistics² of (X, Y) , to reconstruct the sequence. We shall discuss what can be done when the rate is not known to the sender.

A further motivation for the results in this section comes from the scenario where an information source is broadcasted to multiple receivers, each may have some side information regarding the source. Applying Slepian-Wolf scheme in this scenario, using the fact that the sender side is independent of the side infor-

²Universal decoder, such as the MMI decoder, can be used to overcome lack of statistical knowledge, but still the rate must be known in advance [55].

mation raises the problem that for heterogeneous receivers (different amount of side information) a different rate $R_i = H(X|Y_i)$ is needed for each receiver and so the sender may not know for what rate to design the code.

One pessimistic solution for this problem is to use an excess rate. The sender may choose an arbitrary rate R , and if it happens that $H(X|Y) < R$, the receiver can reconstruct the source. Thus, the sender can design the code by knowing or assuming some upper bound on $H(X|Y)$, or in the broadcast scenario, on $H(X|Y_i)$ for all i . In short, the sender must fit its transmission for the worst-case receiver situation. But, is there a way to perform better when the side information allows a better compression? Furthermore, in the broadcast scenario, is it possible for each receiver to get the information only at the rate it needs?

A possible method for the sender to adapt its rate to the minimal required rate is by getting some feedback from the receiver. Feedback, or more generally, interactive communication with the receiver, has been considered in great depth by Orlicsky [58, 59, 60]. In the interactive scenario, the required number of bits needed to be exchanged between the sender (who wants to send the source) and the receiver (who has a side information on the source) has been analyzed both for the worst-case and on average. Note that in interactive communication truly lossless communication (and not only high probability reconstruction) is possible, as the receiver can ask for additional information when necessary. In the context of this section these results assure that the total number of exchanged bits can be upper bounded by the conditional entropy of the source sequence given the side information sequence (which in the IID case is $H_n = \sum_{t=1}^n H(X_t|Y_t)$) *plus* an additional term that is logarithmic with respect to H_n . Thus, by interactive communication, the sender can exchange the information at a close to optimal rate, with no knowledge on the side information and its amount.

Interaction, however, requires two-way communication. In many situations, such as in satellite communication, the backward channel does not exist, or, if it exists, is expensive and has limited capacity. In the broadcast scenario, even if feedback exists and the extra amount of bits exchanged in the interaction is logarithmically small w.r.t. the required number of bits in the forward channel,

this extra amount can be prohibitively excessive, particularly when there are many receivers, as *each* receiver needs to interact with the sender. Is there a way to adapt the sender to the receiver, and yet overcome these problems of feedback and interactive communication?

We present analogous settings for the “static broadcasting” settings and propose similar schemes for the problem discussed here where the sender needs to send (or broadcast) a common source to heterogeneous receivers (or to an unknown receiver).

Suppose we have a block of data x_1^n of the source. As in the static broadcasting case, we allow the receiver to quit when it receives the information needed to reconstruct the data. Here, we simply define the rate as the number of bits received, divided by the fixed data size, n . Note that this definition is actually the reciprocal of the rate defined for static broadcasting, which is the data size divided by the time, or number of received symbols. We claim that we can achieve, for each receiver $H(X|Y_i)$, the conditional entropy of the source given the side information, although the sender may not know the amount of the side information. In the broadcast scenario, our scheme will achieve *simultaneously* the conditional entropy for all receivers. Clearly, this rate cannot be improved.

The proposed scheme associates a (random) bit sequence for each possible value of the source block. The bit sequence corresponding to the source instance is transmitted a bit at a time. The receiver obtains these bits and considers them as the binary expansion, from the least significant bit and forward, of the random index needed for the Slepian-Wolf scheme. By the time K bits are sent, it gets a random index in the range $\{0, \dots, 2^K - 1\}$, and thus if $K > n(H(X|Y_i) + \epsilon)$, the i th receiver can quit, after only receiving its minimal required number of bits.

So far we considered the situation where the transmitter does not know the side information and its amount at the receiver. We now consider an even more complicated scenario in which the decoder has side information on the source but neither the transmitter nor the receiver know the type and amount of the side information.

Figure 4.1 depicts our setting. A source, X , of uniformly, IID, symbols over

alphabet \mathcal{X} generates a sequence of length n (its entropy is $n \log |\mathcal{X}|$). The decoder has some side information on it, Y . The side information corresponds to an unknown discrete conditional probability, $W(Y|X)$, which can be regarded as “unknown channel”. The encoder creates stream of bits (stream of hash bits) from the source, b_1, b_2, \dots . The decoder gets this stream of bits and, with its pre-known side information, sequentially decides when it has enough data to correctly decode the source message.

Figure 4.1: Sequential Slepian-Wolf setting

In the following analysis, the code we use randomly chooses for each of the possible source sequences a *unique* index of $K = \lceil n \log |\mathcal{X}| \rceil$ bits, i.e., the encoder uses a one-to-one function

$$\mathbf{b} : \mathcal{X}^n \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^K.$$

We denote each code sequence by $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}) = (b_1(\mathbf{x}), \dots, b_K(\mathbf{x}))$.

The sequential decoder is essentially the sequential channel decoder presented in Chapter 3 for codewords of length n , where the side information is used as the channel’s output. Now, on each received bit from the encoder the effective size of the “channel code” will be smaller - only source sequences that their hash fits to the received bits will remain in the “channel code”. Since the source is uniformly distributed, all of the source sequences matching the received bits have the same a priori probability. Of course, in the worst case, the decoder will be able to correctly decode the source sequence after receiving the (entire) $\lceil n \log |\mathcal{X}| \rceil$ bits.

Thus, while in the unknown channel case the sequential decoder worked at an effective decreasing rate as time passed given that the code length grew with

each symbol, in the Slepian-Wolf scenario, discussed here, the decreasing rate is due to the decreasing number of codewords, but the “codeword” length is fixed.

After receiving k bits from the encoder, the decoder has M_k possible source sequences to decide from that match the received bits, $b_1^k(\mathbf{x}) = (b_1(\mathbf{x}), \dots, b_k(\mathbf{x}))$. M_k depends on the code, however, as the code contains no repetitions, a simple bound for M_k is

$$M_k \leq 2^{K-k}. \quad (4.3)$$

Since the hashing (the mapping to indices) is random, these possible source sequences are randomly chosen from the entire set *without* repetitions, which can only improve the performance compared to a code that is chosen IID without this restriction.

We shall follow the analysis in Section 3.3, with the difference that now, as time progresses, k increases (the code size decreases), but n stays constant. Hence, we shall use k as the subscript instead of n . Define

$$R_k = \frac{\log M_k}{n} \leq \frac{K-k}{n}.$$

Define U_k as the event that contains the undetected error event after k bits are received, similarly to (3.19), assuming the source sequence is \mathbf{x} and the side information at the decoder is \mathbf{y}

$$U_k = \{ I(\mathbf{x}; \mathbf{y}) < R'_k \text{ and } \exists \mathbf{x}' \neq \mathbf{x}, b_1^k(\mathbf{x}) = b_1^k(\mathbf{x}') \text{ such that } I(\mathbf{x}'; \mathbf{y}) \geq \tilde{R}_k \}.$$

Bounding $\Pr(U_k)$ as in (3.21),

$$\Pr(U_k) \leq (n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1} \exp_2\{-n(\tilde{R}_k - R_k)\} \quad (4.4)$$

and setting

$$R'_k = \tilde{R}_k = R_k + (|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}| + \mu) \frac{\log(n+1)}{n} \quad (4.5)$$

with $\mu > 2$, (4.5) will yield a bound of the probability of undetected error at the decoder as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(\text{error}) &\leq \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \Pr(U_k) \\ &= (K-1)(n+1)^{-\mu+1} \\ &\leq \frac{\log |\mathcal{X}|}{(n+1)^{\mu-2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.6)$$

Note that for $k = K$ we shall not make errors as we are left with only one codeword. As $\mu > 2$ we can achieve any desired small undetected error probability with large enough n .

Defining the decoder's stopping time, N , as the minimal k at which the decoder does not declare an erasure, then, analogously to the unknown channel case

$$\bar{N}(W) \leq 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{K-1} \Pr(A_k(W) \cup B_k(W)). \quad (4.7)$$

Setting $R'_k = \tilde{R}_k$, the sum $\sum \Pr(B_k(W))$ can be bounded like the undetected error probability, and $\Pr(A_k(W))$ decays exponentially with n for k 's that lead to $R_k < I(U; W)$ as in (3.29) where U stands for the uniform distribution. Hence we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{N}(W)}{n} \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{K - nI(U; W)}{n} = \log |X| - I(U; W) = H(U|W). \quad (4.8)$$

Since the opposite inequality is trivial, we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\bar{N}(W)}{n} = H(U|W)$.

Thus, we have shown that a universal scheme with sequential decoder can attain the optimal Slepian-Wolf limits, regardless of the fact that both transmitter and receiver are ignorant of the amount of side information at the receiver.

4.3 Channel Law Known at the Encoder

There are different settings at which the encoder has information on the channel. For example, knowledge of the exact error pattern may enable transmission over a totally noisy channel by subtracting the noise from the codeword before transmitting it [26, 67].

In this short section we describe an interesting scenario where the receiver can be completely ignorant of the channel probabilistic law, yet communication at capacity rate can be achieved. Unlike the Slepian-Wolf scenario, here the "side information" is about a stochastic process, i.e., the channel law, while at the Slepian-Wolf setting the side information is on an instance, i.e., an outcome of a stochastic process.

When the encoder knows the channel law and the receiver does not, the universal scheme presented in Chapter 3 may be used to tune the code to the channel and thus achieve a better rate. Assume the channel's input alphabet is \mathcal{X} . A code for a larger alphabet \mathcal{X}' , $|\mathcal{X}| \ll |\mathcal{X}'|$, can be built, with prior P' over \mathcal{X}' . The encoder, knowing the channel and the maximizing prior, $P^*(x)$, will construct a mapping $\psi : \mathcal{X}' \rightarrow \mathcal{X}$, such that the distribution over \mathcal{X} will be close to the desired one:

$$P(x) = P'(\psi^{-1}(x)) = \sum_{\substack{x' \in \mathcal{X}' \\ \psi(x')=x}} P'(x') \approx P^*(x). \quad (4.9)$$

The decoder will consider the concatenation of the encoder's mapping, ψ (which is unknown to the decoder) and the underlying channel as the effective channel with which it must deal. This channel, W' , has input alphabet \mathcal{X}' . Using Equation (4.9) leads to $I(P'; W') = I(P; W) \approx C(W)$. This scheme can be used with a "regular" block code and an MMI decoder, but in this case, the effective rate is predetermined and cannot be changed according to the actual underlying channel known by the encoder. Utilizing the universal sequential decoder proposed in Section 3.3 leads to a scheme that works with an effective rate that approaches $I(P'; W')$, i.e., close to the channel capacity.

4.4 Summary - Bringing It All Together

In this chapter we have demonstrated the usage of a universal sequential decoder in several scenarios. Common to all these scenarios is the lack of prior knowledge about the feasible rates, i.e., the rates that enable reliable communication.

All scenarios considered in this chapter can be combined in to the following single communication scenario. A compressible source should be transmitted through a noisy channel in the presence of side information at the decoder. This combined setting is depicted in Figure 4.2. The communication scheme works as follows: A block of length K , s_1^K , of the source should be transmitted to the destination. The encoder sends through the channel the infinite codeword x_1, x_2, \dots corresponding to the information message, s_1^K . The decoder has side information z_1^K and it gets, sequentially, symbols from the channel, y_1, y_2, \dots until

it decides upon a decoded message.

Figure 4.2: Generalized Slepian-Wolf setting

This communication setting contains several unknowns:

- Unknown statistics of the source S , and its entropy $H(S)$.
- Unknown statistics of the side information Z , and the entropy of the source given the side information $H(S|Z)$.
- Unknown code's prior P at the decoder (encoder knows it).
- Unknown statistics of the channel W , and its mutual information $I(P; W)$.

The analysis performed above in Section 4.2 cannot be used here as it is assumed there that the stream of bits from the encoder is error free. In the setting examined here, we can simply treat the source and the side information as the input and the output, respectively, of an additional channel, i.e., instead of considering “just” $I_n(x_1^n; y_1^n)$, the decoder uses an extended empirical mutual information metric

$$I(s_1^K, x_1^n; z_1^K, y_1^n) = \frac{nI(x_1^n; y_1^n) + KI(s_1^K; z_1^K)}{n + K},$$

where y and z are the instances that the decoder received, and x indicates the codeword suitable for the the source sequence s .

Combining all of the above results, we constructed a reliable communication scheme whose rate satisfies

$$\lim_{K \rightarrow \infty} \frac{K}{N} = \frac{H(S|Z)}{I(P; W)}, \quad (4.10)$$

where \bar{N} is the average number of channel symbols the sequential decoder uses before declaring a decoded message.

Chapter 5

Universal Encoding - The Prior Problem

A transmitter wanting to communicate over an unknown channel faces several problems. First, the transmitter does not know the rate at which a reliable communication can be maintained as it does not know the channel capacity. Second, the encoder may not know how to design a good code that is tuned to the channel as the code may depend on the unknown optimal capacity achieving prior. The first problem is dealt with in the static broadcast scheme and the universal sequential decoder presented in previous chapters. In this chapter we consider the second problem [73]. We find the optimal input distribution to be used in case the channel is unknown and the degradation it has w.r.t. the optimal distribution. We show that the uniform prior distribution has some universal properties; meaning that the degradation when using it with any possible channel, instead of the optimal prior is, in many cases, minimal. We determine bounds on the amount of the mutual information loss when a uniform prior is used instead of the capacity achieving prior. A related observation is the fact that the capacity achieving prior cannot be very nonuniform. This implies that codes based on a uniform prior assumption, such as linear codes, work well on a large class of channels [53].

To be specific, in this chapter we show the following results:

- In the class of all memoryless channels with the same input alphabet and capacity, the uniform distribution is the prior that maximizes the mini-

mal mutual information. Thus it has the minimal worst-case degradation (measured either by the difference or the ratio) with respect to the capacity.

- For the class of binary input channels with any, even nondiscrete, output alphabet, the Z-channel is the worst binary input channel for the uniform prior, i.e., among all binary input channels with a given capacity, the mutual information induced by the uniform prior is minimal at the Z-channel. As a result, the mutual information induced by the uniform distribution is never less than approximately 0.011 bits than the capacity, and in relative terms it is never less than approximately 6% of the channel capacity.
- The capacity achieving prior, for any channel, can allocate at most a probability mass $1 - e^{-1}$, to any input value. This implies, for binary input, that the mass must be also be at least e^{-1} .
- For nonbinary input alphabet, the maximal degradation in using the uniform prior is not known. We conjecture that a generalized Z-channel has extreme properties analogous to the binary Z-channel. If true, the conjecture would provide the maximal degradation in using the uniform prior; regardless, we show an upper bound on that degradation.

These results on the uniform prior indeed indicate that codes with uniform symbol distribution, e.g., affine codes, or linear codes with possibly a fixed vector added to all codewords, actually work well for a large class of channels.

Much of this chapter extends and proves conjectures discussed in [29], [33], [52] and [74]. Specifically, in [52] it is shown that the capacity achieving prior of any binary input DMC allocates at most $1 - e^{-1}$ to each symbol, but the extension for larger input alphabet is only conjectured. Also in [52] it is shown that the degradation in using the uniform prior is at most 6% for any binary input DMC, but the extreme properties of the Z-channel, and thus the fact that maximal absolute degradation is at most 0.011 bits are not shown there.

In the next section we show the optimal max-min properties of the uniform prior. The results for binary input channels are shown in Section 5.2, and the extension to nonbinary input alphabet is discussed in 5.3.

5.1 The Universal Prior

In this section we explicitly investigate the *universal* prior, i.e., a single predetermined prior that can be used for all channels (and to design codes based on it) so that the loss in using it instead of the optimal prior tuned to channel is monitored. While there may be several criteria to measure the goodness of that prior, here we consider the following criterion: Choose the prior distribution P , so that the rate that can be achieved using it (measured by the mutual information it induces) as compared with the channel capacity, for the worst possible channel, is maximized. In other words we are looking for P that attains

$$\alpha = \max_P \inf_W \frac{I(P; W)}{C(W)}, \quad (5.1)$$

where $C(W) = \max_{P'} I(P'; W)$ is the capacity of the channel W , and the infimum is taken over the class of the possible channels.

Alternatively, we look for P that attains

$$\delta = \min_P \sup_W [C(W) - I(P; W)]. \quad (5.2)$$

In a refined criterion, the universal prior is designed to work well for a class of channels that have the same capacity, $C > 0$. In this case we look for a distribution P (which may depend on C) that attains

$$\beta(C) = \max_P \inf_{\{W: C(W)=C\}} \frac{I(P; W)}{C}. \quad (5.3)$$

Clearly we may have equivalently looked for the max-min of $I(P; W)$ at that class, but in order to relate the criterion to α , defined above, we consider $\beta(C)$, the max-min of $I(P; W)/C$.

In the sequel, the class of channels we consider is the set of all discrete input memoryless channels with a given input alphabet size $A < \infty$ and any (even nondiscrete) output alphabet. When the class of channels is all possible channels with input alphabet of size A , we denote the max-min ratios of (5.1) (5.2) and (5.3) by α_A , δ_A and $\beta_A(C)$, respectively.

Theorem 5.1. *The uniform prior, over the alphabet of size A , attains α_A , δ_A and $\beta_A(C)$ for any C .*

Proof. The theorem is shown by a simple symmetry argument. Assume that a distribution P attains α_A , i.e., solves the max-min problem of (5.1). Given a permutation $\pi \in S_A$, where S_A is the set of all $A!$ permutations of the A symbols, define a probability distribution P_π by $P_\pi(x) = P(\pi(x))$. Due to the problem symmetry, that follows from the fact that all channels with the same input alphabet can be considered, P_π also attains (5.1) for any $\pi \in S_A$. Thus, for any channel W and any permutation π

$$\alpha_A \leq \frac{I(P_\pi; W)}{C(W)}$$

and so, for any W , using the convexity of the mutual information with respect to the input distribution

$$\alpha_A C(W) \leq \sum_{\pi \in S_A} \frac{I(P_\pi; W)}{|S_A|} \leq I(Q; W),$$

where Q is the distribution

$$Q = \sum_{\pi \in S_A} \frac{P_\pi}{|S_A|}.$$

This distribution is, of course, the uniform distribution, regardless of P . Thus, the uniform distribution attains α_A . The same proof holds for δ_A and $\beta_A(C)$. \square

Using the fact that $\beta(C)$ is achieved by the uniform prior for any C we have the following:

Corollary 5.2. $\alpha_A = \inf_C \beta_A(C)$ and $\delta_A = \max_C C(1 - \beta_A(C))$.

The following lemma shows that the relative degradation in using the uniform prior decreases as the channel capacity grows:

Lemma 5.3. $\beta(C)$ increases monotonically with C .

Proof. Given a channel $W(y|x)$, define a new channel $W'(y|x)$ with an additional output symbol, E , as follows:

$$W'(y|x) = \begin{cases} (1 - \epsilon)W(y|x) & \text{if } y \neq E \\ \epsilon & \text{if } y = E. \end{cases}$$

W' is an *erasure* version of W , and for any input prior P we have $I(P; W') = (1 - \epsilon)I(P; W)$ which implies $C(W') = (1 - \epsilon)C(W)$. Now for a given C , assume W leads to $\beta(C)$. Then, for any $C' < C$ we take ϵ such that $C(W') = C'$ and so we have

$$\beta(C) = \frac{I(U; W)}{C(W)} = \frac{I(U; W')}{C(W')} \geq \beta(C').$$

□

Corollary 5.4. $\alpha_A = \lim_{C \rightarrow 0} \beta(C)$.

Later in the chapter we examine the values of α_A , δ_A and $\beta_A(C)$. Interestingly, it will be shown in the next section that the degradation is small for binary input channels. Specifically, α_2 is never smaller than about 0.94, i.e., the relative rate degradation in using uniform distribution is at most 6%. Similarly, the additive degradation δ_2 is at most approximately 0.011 bits. Unfortunately, for large A the degradation can be significant, and in fact $\alpha_A \leq \frac{2}{A}$. To see this, consider the A -ary input channel with binary output, where $W(1|1) = W(2|2) = 1$, $W(1|i) = W(2|i) = 1/2$ for $i = 3, \dots, A$. The capacity of this channel is 1, but with uniform prior U over the entire input alphabet $I(U; W) = \frac{2}{A}$. Nonbinary input channels are discussed in Section 5.3.

5.2 The Binary Input Case

We begin with some preliminary results on the properties of the mutual information of binary input channels needed for our investigation.

Let $q_0(y)$ and $q_1(y)$ be two probability distributions on \mathcal{Y} . Considering \mathcal{Y} as the output alphabet, these two distributions define a binary input channel, Q , where

$$Q(y|0) = q_0(y) \quad \text{and} \quad Q(y|1) = q_1(y). \quad (5.4)$$

We assume that the capacity of the channel Q is greater than zero, i.e., $q_1 \neq q_0$. For an input probability $P(1) = u$ and $P(0) = 1 - u$, the output distribution is

$$q_u(y) = uq_1(y) + (1 - u)q_0(y). \quad (5.5)$$

Define

$$d_0(u) = D(q_0(y)||q_u(y)) = \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} q_0(y) \log \frac{q_0(y)}{q_u(y)} \quad (5.6)$$

$$d_1(u) = D(q_1(y)||q_u(y)) = \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} q_1(y) \log \frac{q_1(y)}{q_u(y)}. \quad (5.7)$$

These functions are strictly monotonic; $d_1(u)$ decreases, $d_0(u)$ increases, and $d_0(0) = d_1(1) = 0$. The mutual information over the channel Q , implied by the input distribution $P(1) = u$, is

$$I(u; Q) = ud_1(u) + (1 - u)d_0(u). \quad (5.8)$$

It is known that the channel's capacity, $C(Q)$, and the input distribution that leads to the mutual information maximization, denoted by u^* , satisfy

$$C(Q) = d_1(u^*) = d_0(u^*). \quad (5.9)$$

Figure 5.1 illustrates typical plots of $d_1(u)$, $d_0(u)$ and $I(u; Q)$, as a function of u .

The derivatives of $d_1(u)$ and $d_0(u)$ with respect to u are given by

$$\begin{aligned} d'_0(u) &= - \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} q_0(y) \frac{q_1(y) - q_0(y)}{q_u(y)} \\ d'_1(u) &= - \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} q_1(y) \frac{q_1(y) - q_0(y)}{q_u(y)}, \end{aligned}$$

which leads to the interesting equalities:

$$ud'_1(u) + (1 - u)d'_0(u) = 0 \quad (5.10)$$

and

$$I'(u; Q) = d_1(u) - d_0(u) \quad (5.11)$$

for any $0 \leq u \leq 1$. Since $d_1(1) = 0$, we have for any $0 \leq \tilde{u} \leq 1$

$$\begin{aligned} d_1(\tilde{u}) &= - \int_{\tilde{u}}^1 d'_1(u) du \\ &= \int_{\tilde{u}}^1 \frac{1 - u}{u} d'_0(u) du \\ &= \int_{\tilde{u}}^1 \frac{1}{u^2} d_0(u) du - \frac{1 - \tilde{u}}{\tilde{u}} d_0(\tilde{u}), \end{aligned} \quad (5.12)$$

Figure 5.1: A typical plot of $d_1(u)$, $d_0(u)$ and $I(u; Q)$.

where the second equality is due to (5.10) and the third is obtained by partial integration. Substituting (5.12) in (5.8) leads to

$$I(\tilde{u}; Q) = \int_{\tilde{u}}^1 \frac{\tilde{u}}{u^2} d_0(u) du. \quad (5.13)$$

The capacity achieving prior is close to uniform

The first result of this section, which is based on the properties shown above, states that the capacity achieving prior, for any binary input channel, cannot be too skewed:

Theorem 5.5. *For any binary input channel, the capacity achieving prior assigns a probability greater than e^{-1} for both symbols.*

Our derivation starts with the following technical lemma whose proof is provided in Appendix C.

Lemma 5.6. *Let $f(x)$ be a positive, nonincreasing function such that $\int_0^1 f(x)dx = 1$, and t solves*

$$\int_0^t \frac{1}{1-x} f(x) dx = 1.$$

Then $t \leq 1 - e^{-1}$, with equality iff $f(x) = 1$ for all $x \in (0, 1)$.

Proof of Theorem 5.5. We may assume that the capacity is greater than zero, since if the capacity is zero, any prior leads to the same, zero, mutual information.

The capacity achieving prior, u^* , satisfies $d_1(u^*) = d_0(u^*)$, and so

$$d_1(0) + \int_0^{u^*} d_1'(u) du = d_0(0) + \int_0^{u^*} d_0'(u) du.$$

Given that $d_0(0) = 0$ we have from (5.10)

$$\int_0^{u^*} \frac{-1}{1-u} d_1'(u) du = d_1(0) = \int_0^1 -d_1'(u) du = D(q_1(y)||q_0(y)).$$

Suppose first that $d_1(0) < \infty$. Using Lemma 5.6 with $f(\cdot) = -d_1'(\cdot)/d_1(0)$, leads to $u^* \leq 1 - e^{-1}$. Equality holds iff $-d_1'(u)/d_1(0) = 1$ for $0 \leq u \leq 1$, but as $d_1'(1) = 0$, this implies that the channel capacity is zero. Thus for the binary channels with nonzero capacity, $u^* < 1 - e^{-1}$.

In case $d_1(0) = \infty$, pick some $0 < \epsilon < u^*$, and define

$$\tilde{d}_1(u) = \begin{cases} d_1(u) & \text{for } u \geq \epsilon \\ d_1(\epsilon) + (u - \epsilon)d_1'(\epsilon) & \text{for } u < \epsilon. \end{cases}$$

Define $\tilde{d}_0(u)$ by $\tilde{d}_0(0) = 0$ and its derivative $\tilde{d}_0'(u) = \frac{-u}{1-u} \tilde{d}_1'(u)$. Let u^+ solve

$$\int_0^{u^+} \tilde{d}_0'(u) - \tilde{d}_1'(u) du = \int_0^{u^+} \frac{-1}{1-u} \tilde{d}_1'(u) du = \tilde{d}_1(0).$$

Since for $u < \epsilon$ we have $\tilde{d}_0'(u) < d_0'(u)$, it follows that $u^+ \geq u^*$. Using this and Lemma 5.6 for u^+ leads to $u^* < u^+ < 1 - e^{-1}$.

We showed, then, that $u^* < 1 - e^{-1}$. Due to symmetry we also have $1 - u^* < 1 - e^{-1}$, i.e., $u^* > e^{-1}$. \square

In view of our derivation, this result has an interesting geometrical interpretation. In solving for the capacity achieving prior, we actually search for a

distribution q satisfying $D(q_1||q) = D(q_0||q)$, where q_1 and q_0 are the output probability given each input symbol, and q is the output probability induced by the capacity achieving prior. This q can be interpreted as the average of q_0 and q_1 in the sense of the divergence. This result indicates that the “divergence average” $q = uq_1 + (1 - u)q_0$ is not far from the arithmetic, Euclidean average $(q_0 + q_1)/2$.

The extreme behavior of the Z-channel

A Z-channel, Z_p , is a binary input binary output channel which is defined by a single parameter, p , $P(0|0) = 1$ and $P(1|1) = p$, as in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: The Z-channel

Denote the input prior $P(1) = u$. For the Z-channel we choose to denote the divergences, $d_1(u)$ and $d_0(u)$, defined above, by

$$z_1(u) = D(\{1 - p, p\} || \{1 - up, up\}) \quad (5.14)$$

$$z_0(u) = D(\{1, 0\} || \{1 - up, up\}) = \log \frac{1}{1 - up}. \quad (5.15)$$

The mutual information over the Z-channel satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} I(u; Z_p) = I_Z(u) &= uz_1(u) + (1 - u)z_0(u) \\ &= h(up) - uh(p), \end{aligned}$$

where $h(p) = -p \log p - (1 - p) \log(1 - p)$ is the binary entropy. The capacity of the Z-channel is $C(Z_p) = \max_u I(u; Z_p)$, where the maximizing u is $u^* = \frac{q^{q/p}}{1 + pq^{q/p}}$, where $q = 1 - p$, see [33].

The following two lemmas demonstrate the extreme behavior of the divergence, $z_0(u)$, and the mutual information $I(u; Z_p)$ as functions of the input prior, u :

Lemma 5.7. *For any binary input channel, with divergence $d_0(\cdot)$ and any Z-channel, if for some $0 < \tilde{u} \leq 1$*

$$z_0(\tilde{u}) = d_0(\tilde{u})$$

then

$$z_0(u) \geq d_0(u)$$

for any $0 \leq u < \tilde{u}$.

The proof of this lemma and an interesting corollary to it are provided in Appendix C.

Lemma 5.8. *Let $I_Z(u) = I(u; Z_p)$ and $I(u) = I(u; Q)$ be the mutual information functions associated with the Z-channel and a general binary input channel Q , respectively, both with input prior satisfying $P(1) = u$. If $I(\tilde{u}) = I_Z(\tilde{u})$ for some $0 < \tilde{u} \leq 1$, then $I(u) \leq I_Z(u)$ for $u \leq \tilde{u}$.*

Again, the proof is given in Appendix C. We are now ready for the main result.

Theorem 5.9. *Among all binary input channels with the same capacity, the Z-channel has the smallest mutual information given uniform input distribution.*

Proof. An equivalent statement of the theorem is that among all binary input channels for which the mutual information induced by a uniform input distribution is the same, the Z-channel has the maximum capacity. We show this statement.

Given any binary input channel, Q , without loss of generality, assume that the capacity achieving prior for Q satisfies $P(1) \leq \frac{1}{2}$. Define a Z-channel, Z_p , such that it has the same mutual information for uniform input distribution. By Lemma 5.8 $I(u; Z_p) \geq I(u; Q)$ for $u \leq 1/2$. Hence

$$C(Z_p) = \max_{0 \leq u \leq 1/2} I(u; Z_p) \geq \max_{0 \leq u \leq 1/2} I(u; Q) = C(Q),$$

which completes the proof. □

Theorem 5.9 implies that $\beta_2(C)$ is the ratio between the mutual information of the Z-channel with the uniform prior, and its capacity. This rate degradation is depicted in Figure 5.3.

The maximal degradation occurs when C (and so p) goes to 0. Golomb showed [33] that the capacity achieving prior of the Z-channel, as $p \rightarrow 0$, is $P(1) = u \rightarrow e^{-1}$. Thus, the value of this maximal degradation is

$$\alpha_2 = \lim_{p \rightarrow 0} \frac{I(1/2; Z_p)}{I(e^{-1}; Z_p)} = \frac{e}{2 \log_2 e} = 0.9420847 \dots ,$$

which is less than 6% loss.

Figure 5.3: $\beta_2(C)$ - Degradation of the rate, when using the uniform prior in the Z-channel

As noted, $\beta_2(C)$ provides a refined bound on the degradation, as a function of the capacity. For example, for channels with $C = 1/2$, the degradation when using the uniform prior is less than $\sim 2\%$.

In terms of absolute values¹,

$$\delta_2 = \min_C C(1 - \beta_2(C)) \approx 0.011 .$$

Hence, the uniform distribution leads to mutual information that is lower than the capacity by ~ 0.011 bits at most. The absolute maximal degradation as a function of the channel capacity, $C(1 - \beta(C))$, is plotted in Figure 5.4.

Figure 5.4: $C(1 - \beta_2(C))$ - Degradation, in bits, when using the uniform prior in the Z-channel

Finally we note that Lemma 5.8 leads to another result: among all binary input channels with the same capacity, the Z-channel has a capacity achieving

¹In order to have the analytical expression, one should solve the equation

$$\frac{1}{2} \log \frac{q}{1+q} = \frac{\log q}{(1-q)q^{-q/1-q} + (1-q)^2}.$$

We used Matlab.

prior which allocates the minimal mass on the symbol '1', which is not smaller than $1/e$. This proves Theorem 5.5, and the result in [52], in yet another way.

5.3 Nonbinary Input Alphabet

This section extends some of the results, shown above for binary input channels, to general input alphabets.

Theorem 5.10. *The capacity achieving prior of any memoryless, discrete-input channel is smaller than $1 - e^{-1}$ for all symbols.*

Proof. Given a channel $W(y|x)$ and capacity achieving input distribution, $P^*(x)$, we wish to show that $P^*(x') < 1 - e^{-1}$, for any x' . Denote by $q(y)$ the output distribution. Then, $D(W(y|x)||q(y)) = C(W)$ for any x such that $P^*(x) > 0$. Assume $P^*(x') > 0$. Create the following binary input channel:

$$\begin{aligned} Q(y|0) &= W(y|x') \\ Q(y|1) &= \frac{1}{1 - P^*(x')} \sum_{x \neq x'} P^*(x) W(y|x). \end{aligned}$$

Using $P(0) = P^*(x')$, $P(1) = 1 - P^*(x')$ as the input distribution to the channel, Q leads to the same $q(y)$ as the output distribution. Due to the convexity of the divergence we have

$$D(Q(y|0)||q(y)) = C(W) \geq D(Q(y|1)||q(y)).$$

Hence, the capacity achieving prior for this binary input channel gives greater or equal probability for the symbol 0 than $P^*(x')$. Thus, using Theorem 5.5 we have $P^*(x') < 1 - e^{-1}$. \square

Another bound on the capacity achieving prior is given in the following lemma.

Lemma 5.11. *Consider a memoryless channel with a discrete input alphabet and a capacity C . Let P^* be the capacity achieving prior. Then, for each input symbol x we have*

$$P^*(x) \leq 2^{-C}.$$

The proof is in Appendix C.

Generalized Z-channel: This channel is defined by 3 parameters: A is the input alphabet size, $1 < A_e \leq A$ is the output size (and the “effective” input size), and $0 \leq p \leq 1$ as follows:

$$Z_p^{A_e}(y|x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x < A_e \text{ and } y = x \\ 0 & \text{if } x < A_e \text{ and } y \neq x \\ p & \text{if } x = A_e \text{ and } y = x \\ (A_e - 1)^{-1}(1 - p) & \text{if } x = A_e \text{ and } y \neq x \\ A_e^{-1} \sum_{x'=1}^{A_e} Z_p^{A_e}(y|x') & \text{if } x > A_e . \end{cases} \quad (5.16)$$

Note that the input symbols greater than A_e are not used to achieve the capacity, and they contribute 0 to the mutual information when uniform distribution on the input symbols is used. In Figure 5.5 there is a generalized Z-channel with $A = 4, A_e = 3$.

Figure 5.5: Generalized Z-channel, $A = 4, A_e = 3$

Due to the symmetry between the $A_e - 1$ symbols, the capacity achieving input distribution is of the form $P(x = A_e) = u$, and $P(x) = \frac{1-u}{A_e-1}$ for $x < A_e$:

$$I(u; Z_p^{A_e}) = h(up) - uh(p) + (1 - u) \log(A_e - 1).$$

Following [33], the capacity achieving prior is

$$u^* = \frac{q^{q/p}}{(A_e - 1)^{1/p} + pq^{q/p}},$$

where $q = 1 - p$. For $p \rightarrow 0$, unlike the binary case ($A_e = 2$) for which $u \rightarrow e^{-1}$, in general $u^* \rightarrow 0$. This is an example that for nonbinary input channels there is no “minimum probability” for each of the (used) input symbols.

Substituting u^* , we obtain the capacity of the generalized Z-channel:

$$C(Z_p^{A_e}) = \log \left(A_e - 1 + \left(\frac{pq}{A_e - 1} \right)^{q/p} \right). \quad (5.17)$$

As seen easily from the definition of the channel, for each value of $C \leq \log A$, choosing A_e to be the minimal value such that $C < \log A_e$ there is a value for p that will lead to a generalized Z-channel with capacity C .

The mutual information over this channel, given a uniform distribution U over all A input symbols, is:

$$I(U; Z_p^{A_e}) = A_e A^{-1} (h(A_e^{-1}p) - A_e^{-1}h(p) + (1 - A_e^{-1}) \log(A_e - 1)).$$

Conjecture 5.12. *For a memoryless channel with input alphabet size A , $\beta_A(C)$ is achieved by the generalized Z-channel.*

If the conjecture is true, for a given capacity, C , $\beta_A(C) \propto \frac{1}{A}$ for A 's greater or equal to 2^C , and in particular

$$\alpha_A = \frac{2}{A} \alpha_2 = \frac{e}{A \log_2 e}.$$

The generalized Z-channel provides an upper bound on $\beta_A(C)$, and it is conjectured that this bound is the actual value. In the sequel we derive a lower bound on $\beta_A(C)$.

The following lemma bounds the ratio between the mutual information associated with two input probabilities in terms of the ratio between these probabilities. The proof for this lemma is in Appendix C.

Lemma 5.13. *Given a channel, W , and two prior distributions P and P' , then*

$$\frac{I(P; W)}{I(P'; W)} \geq \min_x \frac{P(x)}{P'(x)}.$$

Combining Lemma 5.13, Theorem 5.10 and Lemma 5.11 we obtain for a memoryless channel with discrete input alphabet of size A the following lower bound:

$$\beta_A(C) \geq \frac{1}{A \min(2^{-C}, 1 - e^{-1})}. \quad (5.18)$$

This lower bound is equal to the upper bound induced by the generalized Z-channel when 2^C is integer. Hence:

Corollary 5.14. *For a memoryless channel with input alphabet size of A , if K is an integer such that $2 \leq K \leq A$ then*

$$\beta_A(\log K) = \frac{K}{A} . \quad (5.19)$$

Finally, we show simulation results that provide some insight on the value of $\beta_A(C)$. Interestingly, while we were unable to prove the conjecture above, the simulation indicates its validity, as shown in Figure 5.6. In this simulation, channels with input and output alphabet of size 4 were selected randomly². For each chosen channel we calculated the capacity and the mutual information associated with the uniform prior. The simulation contained more than a million points. The fact that none of the randomly selected channels supplied a counterexample for our conjecture on $\beta_A(C)$, and that many examples are on the border implied by the conjecture, indeed supports the conjecture validity. Also note that for this case of $A=4$, the conjecture leads to $\delta_4 = 0.5$, while the lower bound we proved leads to $\delta_4 \leq 0.512$. Thus in terms of the difference in bits, the degradation in using the uniform prior is estimated quite well. Unfortunately, it is not as low as 0.011 bits, shown for binary input channels.

5.4 Summary

In this chapter we showed the important optimal property of the uniform distribution, that it attains, universally over all discrete input memoryless channels, the maximal mutual information. We further showed that for binary input channels the degradation in using it, instead of the true capacity achieving prior, is the worst for the Z-channel, and the amount of that degradation is quite small.

The optimal properties of the uniform prior were largely observed, e.g., [53]. We add to that the fact that the expurgated error exponent for any binary input channels is maximized by the uniform distribution [30]. All these results indicate that codes designed, implicitly or explicitly, with a uniform prior can work well for a large class of discrete input channels. A similar claim that has been observed

²We used a “smart” lottery scheme in order to have good coverage of the different types of channels.

Figure 5.6: Degradation simulation results for $A = 4$

in practice is to use codes designed for a Gaussian prior for channels with additive noise and power constraint. A recent result shown by Zamir and Erez [84] analyzes the loss in using the Gaussian prior. We indicate that the Gaussian distribution can be essentially regarded as a uniform distribution over a large dimension ball, whose radius represents the power constraint. However, in this and other similar cases, the problem of finding an optimal, max-min result, analogous to what we have shown here, remains unsolved.

Chapter 6

Periodic Codes - The Complexity Problem

Communicating fixed-size messages over low capacity channels requires a code with long codewords. When the message is communicated over an unknown channel, it may turn out that the channel's capacity is infinitely small requiring codewords with unbounded length. The complexity of creating, encoding and decoding long codewords may be prohibitively high. In this chapter we show that in the case of low rate codes, periodic codes can be used without significant loss in the achievable transmission rate.

6.1 Periodic Codes

A code over alphabet \mathcal{X} with length N , $\mathcal{C} \subset \mathcal{X}^N$ is said to be periodic with period length $T < N$ if each codeword $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{C}$ satisfies $x_i = x_{i+T}$ for $1 \leq i \leq N - T$. The number of periods is $k = N/T$, which in general may be noninteger.

If a finite periodic code with $N = kT$ is used over memoryless channels, the code is essentially a k -repetitions code. If k is not an integer, then part of the symbols are repeated $[k]$ and the rest are repeated one time less.

Given a DMC and an input prior, the achievable rate of a general code based on this prior is $I(X; Y)$, where X and Y are random variables associated with the channel's input and output. When a repetition code with k repetitions is used over this channel, the achievable rate is $\frac{1}{k}I(X; Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_k)$ where the Y_1, \dots, Y_k

are independent outcomes of the channel given the same X . Thus, if

$$\frac{1}{k}I(X; Y_1^k) \approx I(X; Y), \quad (6.1)$$

there is no significant loss in using periodic codes.

The analysis to follow later in this chapter assumes a uniform input prior. As shown in Chapter 5, a uniform prior is the “universal” choice. Furthermore, as the symbols are repeated, these input symbols can be estimated better, resulting in a cleaner¹ effective channel. For a clean channel, the uniform distribution is optimal in the sense of maximizing the information rate. Thus as more repetitions are used, the uniform choice we assume is closer to optimal.

Consider now the following Markov chain, $Y \ominus X \ominus Y'$, i.e., three random variables satisfy that Y and Y' are independent given X . In terms of probability distributions² $p(y', x, y) = p(x)p(y|x)p(y'|x)$. This Markov chain is interesting, as Y and Y' may represent different (sets of) channel output which are independent given the input X . For Markov chain we have $I(X; Y, Y') = I(X; Y) + I(X; Y') - I(Y; Y')$. The following lemma bounds $I(Y; Y')$ in terms of $I(X; Y)$ and $I(X; Y')$, and thus it is useful in analyzing (6.1).

Lemma 6.1. *Let $Y \ominus X \ominus Y'$ be a Markov chain, and let X be a uniformly distributed A -ary random variable. Then $I(Y; Y') \leq \frac{A^2}{\log e} I(Y; X)I(X; Y')$.*

The requirement that X is uniformly distributed is essential. For example, taking $X = Y = Y'$, $I(Y; Y') = I(X; Y) = H(X)$ can be significantly larger than $H^2(X)$ if $H(X) \ll 1$, which can happen only if X is not uniformly distributed.

Proof. Define

$$\delta(x|y) = p(x|y) - p(x) \quad \text{and} \quad \delta'(x|y') = p(x|y') - p(x). \quad (6.2)$$

¹When the number of repetitions goes to infinity, the input symbol can be estimated exactly, as long as the conditional output distribution is different for each input symbol, resulting in a clean channel.

²In this chapter, to simplify the formulation, we distinguish between the various probability distributions and functions by their argument names, e.g., $p(y) = \Pr(Y = y)$ and $p(x|y') = \Pr(X = x|Y' = y')$.

Using this definition we have

$$I(X; Y) = \sum_y p(y) \sum_x p(x|y) \log \frac{p(x|y)}{p(x)} \geq \frac{\log e}{2} \sum_y p(y) \left(\sum_x |\delta(x|y)| \right)^2, \quad (6.3)$$

where the last inequality is due to Pinsker's inequality that asserts

$$D(P(x)||Q(x)) \geq \frac{\log e}{2} \|P - Q\|_1^2 = \frac{\log e}{2} \left(\sum_x |P(x) - Q(x)| \right)^2$$

for any two distributions, P and Q .

Under the assumption that X is uniformly distributed, i.e., $p(x) = \frac{1}{A}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} p(y'|y) &= \sum_x p(x|y)p(y'|x) = \sum_x p(x|y) \frac{p(x|y')p(y')}{p(x)} \\ &= p(y') \sum_x \frac{(p(x) + \delta(x|y))(p(x) + \delta'(x|y'))}{p(x)} \\ &= p(y') A \sum_x \left(\frac{1}{A} + \delta(x|y) \right) \left(\frac{1}{A} + \delta'(x|y') \right) \\ &= p(y') \left(1 + A \sum_x \delta(x|y)\delta'(x|y') \right), \end{aligned} \quad (6.4)$$

where the last equality follows, as $\sum_x \delta(x|y) = 0$. Substituting (6.4) in the expression for $I(Y; Y')$ yields:

$$\begin{aligned} I(Y; Y') &= \sum_y p(y) \sum_{y'} p(y'|y) \log \frac{p(y'|y)}{p(y')} \\ &= \sum_y p(y) \sum_{y'} p(y') \left(1 + A \sum_x \delta(x|y)\delta'(x|y') \right) \log \left(1 + A \sum_x \delta(x|y)\delta'(x|y') \right) \\ &\stackrel{(a)}{\leq} \log e \sum_y p(y) \sum_{y'} p(y') \left(1 + A \sum_x \delta(x|y)\delta'(x|y') \right) \left(A \sum_x \delta(x|y)\delta'(x|y') \right) \\ &\stackrel{(b)}{=} A^2 \log e \sum_y p(y) \sum_{y'} p(y') \left(\sum_x \delta(x|y)\delta'(x|y') \right)^2 \\ &\stackrel{(c)}{\leq} \frac{1}{4} A^2 \log e \sum_y p(y) \sum_{y'} p(y') \left(\sum_x |\delta(x|y)| \right)^2 \left(\sum_{x'} |\delta'(x|y')| \right)^2 \\ &\stackrel{(d)}{\leq} \frac{A^2}{\log e} I(X; Y) \cdot I(X; Y'), \end{aligned}$$

where (a) follows as $\log(1+x) \leq x \log e$, (b) since $\sum_{y'} p(y') \delta(x|y') = 0$, (c) is due to the inequality $\sum a_i b_i \leq \frac{1}{2} \sum |a_i| \sum |b_i|$ if $\sum b_i = 0$ and (d) follows from (6.3). \square

The chain of inequalities in the proof above is not tight, as each is tight for different values of the parameters, and some do not use all the constraints on the parameters. Hence, a better factor than $\frac{A^2}{\log e}$ may be obtained. Nevertheless, the following example shows that this factor must be at least $\frac{1}{h(A^{-1})}$, where $h(\cdot)$ is the binary entropy: Consider a *clean* channel with input alphabet of size A and binary output alphabet. One of the input symbols is mapped (with probability one) to the output symbol 0 while the rest are mapped to 1. Let X be uniformly distributed over the input alphabet, and let Y and Y' be independent outcomes of the channel for the input X . Then $I(X; Y) = I(X; Y') = I(Y; Y') = h(A^{-1})$, which leads to $I(Y; Y') = \frac{1}{h(A^{-1})} I(X; Y) I(X; Y')$ for this specific channel.

Lemma 6.1 is now used to prove the next lemma, the objective of which is to show the validity of equation (6.1) under specific conditions.

Lemma 6.2. *Consider a channel with input alphabet, \mathcal{X} , of size A . Let X be uniformly distributed over \mathcal{X} , and let Y, Y_1, Y_2, \dots be independent outcomes of the channel for the same input X . Then for any integer k*

$$I(X; Y_1^k) \geq kI(X; Y) \left(1 - \frac{k-1}{2} \gamma I(X; Y) \right), \quad (6.5)$$

where $\gamma = \frac{A^2}{\log e}$.

Proof. If $\gamma I(X; Y) \geq 1$ then the proof is trivial as $I(X; Y_1^k) \geq 0$ and it is nondecreasing with k . For $\gamma I(X; Y) < 1$ we prove by induction. For $k = 1$ it is trivial. Assume that the lemma holds for k , we need to prove its correctness for $k + 1$.

$$\begin{aligned} I(X; Y_1^{k+1}) &\stackrel{(a)}{=} I(X; Y_1^k) + I(X; Y_{k+1}) - I(Y_1^k; Y_{k+1}) \\ &\stackrel{(b)}{\geq} I(X; Y_1^k) + I(X; Y_{k+1}) - \gamma I(X; Y_1^k) I(X; Y_{k+1}) \\ &\stackrel{(c)}{\geq} \left(kI(X; Y) - \gamma \frac{k(k-1)}{2} I^2(X; Y) \right) (1 - \gamma I(X; Y)) + I(X; Y) \\ &\stackrel{(d)}{\geq} (k+1)I(X; Y) - \gamma \frac{k(k+1)}{2} I^2(X; Y), \end{aligned} \quad (6.6)$$

where (a) follows given that the Y 's are independent given X , (b) by using Lemma 6.1, (c) by using $\gamma I(X; Y) < 1$, $I(X; Y_{k+1}) = I(X; Y)$ and the induction assumption and (d) follows by dropping the positive term $\gamma^{2\frac{k(k-1)}{2}} I^3(X; Y)$. \square

This lemma demonstrates that if $I(X; Y) \ll \frac{1}{\gamma^k}$, then a code with k repetitions does not cause much degradation in the mutual information, i.e., equation (6.1) essentially holds.

The channel coding theorem asserts that communication over a DMC, W , at any desirably small positive error probability and for any rate $R < I(U; W)$ is possible using a large enough code randomly selected with uniform prior U . The following theorem provides a similar statement in the case where the code is periodic.

Theorem 6.3. *Given a DMC, W , and an integer number of periods, k , then for any $\epsilon > 0$ and any $R < I(U; W) (1 - \frac{k-1}{2}\gamma I(U; W))$, where U is a uniform prior and $\gamma = \frac{A^2}{\log e}$, there exists a periodic code with k periods and 2^K codewords of length $N \leq \frac{K}{R}$ and period length $T = \frac{N}{k}$, such that decoding error probability is smaller than ϵ , for large enough K .*

Proof. Assuming the input and output alphabets of W are \mathcal{X} and \mathcal{Y} , respectively, define W^k to be a channel from \mathcal{X} to \mathcal{Y}^k such that

$$W^k(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k | x) = \prod_{i=1}^k W(y_i | x). \quad (6.7)$$

Using Lemma 6.2, $I(U; W^k) \geq k (I(U; W) - \frac{k-1}{2}\gamma I^2(U; W))$. Using the channel coding theorem, for any rate $R' < I(U; W^k)$ and large enough N' there exists a code, \mathcal{C}' , of length N' whose decoding error probability is less than ϵ when used over W^k . Building a periodic code of length $N = kN'$ by repeating each codeword in \mathcal{C}' k times, yields a code whose rate is $R = R'/k$ which when used over W has the same error probability. \square

The above theorem can be easily extended to noninteger k by separately considering the prefix of the period that is repeated $\lceil k \rceil$ times and the suffix that is repeated $\lfloor k \rfloor$ times.

6.2 Converse - Repetition Creates Positive Degradation

We have shown an upper bound to the degradation in the mutual information due to repetition. In this section we demonstrate that there must be a *strictly* positive degradation, even if small, in using periodic codes.

We prove that there must be a positive degradation by showing in the lemma below that two independent outcomes Y_1, Y_2 of a DMC with the same uniform input X must be dependent, i.e., $I(Y_1; Y_2) > 0$ (leading to $I(X; Y_1, Y_2) > I(X; Y_1) + I(X; Y_2)$), if the channel has a positive capacity.

It should be noted, however, that for a general Markov chain $Y \ominus X \ominus Y'$, Y and Y' can be independent. For example, let Y and Y' be independent random variables, and let $X = (Y, Y')$, thus $I(X; Y, Y') = I(X; Y) + I(X; Y')$, and still $Y \ominus X \ominus Y'$ is a Markov chain.

Lemma 6.4. *Let Y_1 and Y_2 be two independent outcomes of a memoryless channel with the same input, X . If $I(X; Y) > 0$ then $I(Y_1; Y_2) > 0$.*

Proof. Consider the probability that Y_1 equals Y_2 ,

$$\begin{aligned} \Pr(Y_1 = Y_2) &= \sum_y \sum_x p(x) p^2(y|x) \\ &\geq \sum_y \left(\sum_x p(x) p(y|x) \right)^2 \\ &= \sum_y p^2(y). \end{aligned}$$

The inequality follows Jensen's inequality for the convex function $f(x) = x^2$. Equality holds iff for each y , $p(y|x)$ does not depend on x , i.e., only if $I(X; Y) = 0$. Thus, under the conditions of the lemma, $\Pr(Y_1 = Y_2) > \sum_y p^2(y)$. In contrast, if Y_1 and Y_2 are independent, $\Pr(Y_1 = Y_2) = \sum_y p^2(y)$. Hence, Y_1 and Y_2 cannot be independent. \square

The following corollary states that there is *always* a positive degradation if periodic codes are used, even if very small:

Corollary 6.5. *If Y_1, Y_2, \dots are independent outcomes of a channel for the same input X , and $I(X; Y) > 0$, then for any integer $k \geq 2$*

$$I(X; Y_1^k) < kI(X; Y).$$

Proof. For $k = 2$ it follows directly from the lemma above. For $k > 2$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} I(X; Y_1^k) &\leq I(X; Y_1, Y_2) + I(X; Y_3^k) \\ &< I(X; Y_1) + I(X; Y_2) + (k-2)I(X; Y) \\ &\leq kI(X; Y), \end{aligned}$$

where the strict inequality follows from the lemma above. □

6.3 Static Broadcasting and Periodic Codes

The static broadcasting concept introduced in Chapter 2 considers the case where there is a fixed-size message to be transmitted to multiple receivers or to be transmitted over an unknown channel. The codewords, in essence, are constructed so that their length is eventually as large as required by the worst channel, and each receiver uses a prefix of the code that it needs to decode the message. Suppose that the worst channel has a diminishing capacity. This happens, for example, when the class of channels is all DMCs with a given input alphabet. In this case the code length is unbounded. An alternative to construct an infinite length code is to generate a code of some length T , and periodically repeat it as required. This will lead to some degradation in performance, which we now analyze following the results of the previous sections.

We assume below that the channel in use is DMC, denoted W , and that a uniform prior U is used for generating the codes. Furthermore, N will denote the codeword length needed by the channel in use, i.e., the receiver over that channel extracts a prefix of size N of the possibly infinite transmitted codeword. Denoting by X, Y the channel input and output. Clearly, since the code is periodic with period T , we have $I(X_1^N; Y_1^N) = I(X_1^T; Y_1^N)$. In general $k = N/T$ is not an integer, and so some of the symbols are repeated $[k]$ and some $[k] + 1$. Define

$r = k - \lfloor k \rfloor$. We have the following lower bound on $I(X_1^N; Y_1^N)$, for the periodic code case, in terms of the single letter mutual information $I(U; W)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I(X_1^T; Y_1^N) &\stackrel{(a)}{\geq} (1-r)T \left(\lfloor k \rfloor I(U; W) - \frac{(\lfloor k \rfloor - 1)\lfloor k \rfloor \gamma}{2} I^2(U; W) \right) + \\
 &\quad rT \left((\lfloor k \rfloor + 1)I(U; W) - \frac{\lfloor k \rfloor(\lfloor k \rfloor + 1)\gamma}{2} I^2(U; W) \right) \\
 &\stackrel{(b)}{=} NI(U; W) - \frac{1}{2}T\gamma I^2(U; W)\lfloor k \rfloor(k+r-1) \\
 &\stackrel{(c)}{\geq} NI(U; W) - \frac{1}{2}T\gamma(k-0.5)^2 I^2(U; W), \tag{6.8}
 \end{aligned}$$

where (a) is due to Lemma 6.2 and the fact that there are rT symbols that repeat $\lfloor k \rfloor + 1$ times and $(1-r)T$ symbols that repeat $\lfloor k \rfloor$. (b) is simply since $k = (1-r)\lfloor k \rfloor + r(\lfloor k \rfloor + 1)$ and (c) follows since for $0 \leq r < 1$ we have $(k-r)(k+r-1) \geq (k-0.5)^2$.

As noted above, when a periodic code is used, some degradation is expected. This degradation, however, may be different for each channel since each may need a different number of periods. Nevertheless, a uniform bound on the degradation can be found. To be specific, let K be the length, in bits, of the information message, and so $R = K/N$ is the rate of the periodic code we use. Define the degradation ratio μ of the periodic code by $\mu = R/I(U; W)$, as $I(U; W)$ is the maximal rate that can be achieved with a code based on the uniform prior over the channel W . The following lemma provides a lower bound on μ which depends only on $t = T/K$:

Lemma 6.6. *For any $0 < \mu < 1$ there exists a periodic code with a period length $T = tK$, K is the number of information bits, and*

$$t \leq \begin{cases} \frac{\gamma}{2\mu(1-\mu)} & \text{if } \mu \geq \frac{1}{2} \\ 2\gamma & \text{if } \mu < \frac{1}{2}, \end{cases} \tag{6.9}$$

where $\gamma = \frac{A^2}{\log e}$, whose degradation ratio is at least μ for all DMCs with a given input alphabet A .

Note that t is the factor by which the information bits are expanded in a single period of the code. The lemma states that we can find such a factor for

all possible DMCs, which may depend on the desired degradation ratio and on the input alphabet, but is independent of the channel in use and its mutual information.

Proof. The highest achievable rate for reliable communication over a given channel W using a uniform input prior is $R = I(U; W)$. From equation (6.8), a lower bound on that maximal achievable rate, R , when using a periodic code with k periods, is $R \geq I(U; W) - \frac{T}{2N}\gamma(k - 0.5)^2 I^2(U; W)$. Hence there exists a periodic code for reliable communication whose degradation ratio satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= \frac{R}{I(U; W)} \\ &\geq 1 - \frac{(k - 0.5)^2}{2k} \gamma I(U; W) \\ &= 1 - \frac{(k - 0.5)^2 \gamma}{2k^2 t \mu} \\ &> 1 - \frac{\gamma}{2t\mu}, \end{aligned} \tag{6.10}$$

where $k = N/T$, $R = K/N$, $T = tK$ and assuming $k > \frac{1}{2}$. Notice that for $\mu \geq \frac{1}{2}$ inequality (6.10) is equivalent to (6.9). The proof is completed by noting that if some expansion factor t is sufficient for a degradation ratio μ^* , it is also sufficient for any $\mu < \mu^*$. Thus, for $\mu < \frac{1}{2}$ it is sufficient to have $t = 2\gamma$. \square

Given a desired degradation ratio μ , the lemma above provides an upper bound for the expansion factor t of each period, that leads to a periodic code with that degradation ratio or better. Figure 6.1 illustrates the lower bound on the achievable μ as a function of t , that follows from this lemma.

The above bound on μ is independent of $I(U; W)$. Also note that it becomes less tight as k decreases ($I(U; W)$ increases). Taking into account the actual value of $I(U; W)$ may lead to a better bound on μ .

The following corollary of Lemma 6.6 relates the results above on periodic codes to static broadcasting:

Corollary 6.7. *Static broadcasting with periodic codes, of period $T = tK$, $t \geq 2\gamma$, to the set of DMCs $\{W_\theta : \theta \in \Theta\}$, with input alphabet size A , attains the rate*

Figure 6.1: Degradation ratio of the achievable rate with respect to the mutual information with uniform prior, when using periodic code, with period length T .

point $\{R_\theta = \mu I(U; W_\theta) : \theta \in \Theta\}$, where

$$\mu = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \frac{2\gamma}{t}} \right), \quad (6.11)$$

and $\gamma = \frac{A^2}{\log e}$.

6.4 Examples

We present below two examples where we provide an exact calculation of the degradation that periodic codes cause. In the first example we examine the case of erasure channels with different erasure probabilities, and in the second example we analyze the (nondiscrete) case of additive memoryless Gaussian channels with different signal to noise ratios.

6.4.1 The erasure channels case

The erasure channel is the simplest example to demonstrate the properties of periodic codes. Using repetitions over an erasure channel effectively yields an erasure channel, with a smaller erasure probability³. Specifically, let ε be the erasure probability. For k times repetition, the effective erasure probability is ε^k . Assuming uniform input distribution we have

$$I(X; Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_k) = 1 - \varepsilon^k = \sum_{i=1}^k (-1)^{i+1} \binom{k}{i} (1 - \varepsilon)^i, \quad (6.12)$$

and

$$I(Y_1; Y_2) = (1 - \varepsilon)^2 = I^2(X; Y),$$

$$I(Y_{k+1}; Y_{k+2} | Y_1^k) = \varepsilon^k (1 - \varepsilon)^2.$$

For low capacity channels, $1 - \varepsilon \ll 1$, a lower bound of (6.12), accurate up to $O((1 - \varepsilon)^3)$ terms is

$$I(X; Y_1^k) > k(1 - \varepsilon) - \binom{k}{2} (1 - \varepsilon)^2.$$

This quadratic bound is similar to (6.6). Indeed, by using Lemmas 6.1 and 6.2 we could have deduced relations similar to the above equations, but here, for the erasure case, we were able to obtain more refined relations with $\gamma = 1$.

In the erasure case it is possible to derive a tight bound on the rate degradation with respect to the capacity $C = I(U; W) = 1 - \varepsilon$, when using periodic codes period length $T = tK$ and uniform prior. First, note that the degradation per symbol strictly increases as the number of repetitions increases. Hence, the maximal degradation (minimal μ) occurs as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 1$. In this case, the number of repetitions, k , goes to infinity, and we may assume it is an integer. In that case, the maximal achievable rate is $R = \frac{1 - \varepsilon^k}{k}$. But since we also have $R = K/N = K/kT = 1/kt$ we get

$$k = \frac{\log(1 - \frac{1}{t})}{\log \varepsilon}.$$

³Note that the Z-channel has a similar property.

Hence, the degradation ratio as function of the channel erasure probability, ε , and of the “normalized” period length, $t = T/K$ (for values of ε and t where k above is an integer) is

$$\mu(t; \varepsilon) = \frac{R}{C} = \frac{1/kt}{1 - \varepsilon} = \frac{1}{t \log(1 - \frac{1}{t})} \frac{\log \varepsilon}{1 - \varepsilon}.$$

The expression $\frac{\log \varepsilon}{1 - \varepsilon}$ increases monotonically with ε and thus it can be bounded by $\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 1} \frac{\log \varepsilon}{1 - \varepsilon} = -\log e$. Hence we have

$$\mu = \mu(t) \geq \frac{-\log e}{t \log(1 - \frac{1}{t})}. \quad (6.13)$$

Note that for $t > 1$ μ is strictly positive and that μ goes to 1 as t grows, since $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} (1 - 1/x)^x = 1/e$.

The erasure channel is simple enough, so that the case of a nonuniform input prior can be analyzed for it as well. For an erasure channel with nonuniformly distributed input X (and a possibly large alphabet) we have

$$I(X; Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_k) = (1 - \varepsilon^k)H(X).$$

In this case $I(Y_1; Y_2) = \frac{I(X; Y_1)I(X; Y_2)}{H(X)}$. This may imply that in general we can extend Lemma 6.1 to the case of a nonuniform prior and expect that the entropy of X will be taken into account (in some way) in the bound for $I(Y; Y')$, the mutual information between the two random variables in the ends of the Markov chain.

6.4.2 The Gaussian channels case

The Gaussian channel is not a discrete channel, but yet, it holds the property that at a low signal to noise ratio (SNR) repetition does not cause a major degradation in the achievable rate. Specifically, assume that the input is normally distributed $X \sim N(0, S)$, and the noise is distributed $Z \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$. The output of the channel is $Y = X + Z$. When the signal to noise ratio is small, $\rho = \frac{S}{\sigma^2} \ll 1$, the capacity can be approximated as

$$C = I(X; Y) = \frac{1}{2} \log(1 + \rho) \approx \frac{\rho}{2} \log e.$$

When the input symbol is repeated k times, the best utilization of these repetitions is to average the corresponding k output symbols, and effectively get a Gaussian channel with a reduced noise variance of σ^2/k . Hence

$$I(X; Y_1, \dots, Y_k) = \frac{1}{2} \log(1 + k\rho) \approx kC$$

where the approximation is valid for $\rho \ll \frac{1}{k}$, meaning $C \ll \frac{1}{k}$.

A tight bound for the degradation over the additive Gaussian channel when using periodic codes can be achieved. Similarly to the erasure case, the degradation is maximal as k goes to infinity (ρ goes to zero), and we can assume again that k is an integer. Since the maximal achievable rate is $R = \frac{\log(1+k\rho)}{2k}$ and also $R = 1/kt$ we have

$$k = \frac{2^{(2/t)} - 1}{\rho}.$$

Hence, the degradation ratio as function of the channel signal to noise ratio, ρ , and of the “normalized” period length, $t = T/K$ (for values of ρ and t where k above is an integer) is

$$\mu(t; \rho) = \frac{R}{C} = \frac{2}{kt \log(1 + \rho)} = \frac{2\rho}{t(2^{(2/t)} - 1) \log(1 + \rho)}.$$

This expression decreases monotonically with ρ and as $\lim_{\rho \rightarrow 0} \frac{\rho}{\log(1+\rho)} = 1/\log e$ we have

$$\mu = \mu(t) \geq \frac{2/\log e}{t(2^{(2/t)} - 1)}. \quad (6.14)$$

This bound, as well as the bound in (6.13) for the erasure case, are depicted in Figure 6.2.

Note that while in the (binary) erasure case, $\mu = 0$ for $t < 1$, in the Gaussian case $\mu > 0$ for any $t > 0$. This is since in the erasure case there is insufficient information in a single period even if the channel is noiseless when $t < 1$. However, in the Gaussian case even a period of one symbol is sufficient, given that as the number of repetitions goes to infinity, this repeated symbol may contain an unbounded amount of information, and hence μ is positive for any $t > 0$.

Figure 6.2: Degradation ratio with respect to capacity, when using periodic code over erasure channel and additive Gaussian channel with period length T .

6.5 Further Discussion

In this chapter we examined and analyzed the mutual information function in repetition codes and in periodic codes, where in the latter case the number of repetitions is a function of the channel “quality”. Based on these results and the classical channel coding theorem, we have derived bounds on the achievable rates for periodic codes as a function of the period length (normalized by the message size). However, we did not investigate the periodic codes under the more complex settings that were reviewed in the previous chapters. Periodic codes have a constrained structure, and thus extending the results that assume and use totally random codes to periodic codes may not be straightforward. For example, using infinite random codes ensures that the universal sequential decoder in Chapter 3 will stop with probability one. In the case of periodic codes, there is a nonzero

probability that two infinite periodic codewords will be equal, and in that case the universal sequential decoder will never stop. This problem can be partially solved by using a specific good code as the basic period of the periodic code. This ensures that the sequential decoder will stop. A good code that fits all DMCs, may be based on results in [17, 18].

Another point that should be considered is the difference between the ML decoder and the MMI decoder. In the analysis of the MMI decoder, the number of joint types of the input and output alphabets is a polynomial factor in the derived bounds. This may cause a problem for periodic codes. To see this, assume a DMC W with output alphabet \mathcal{Y} ; with k periods, the channel W^k as defined in (6.7) has effectively an output alphabet of size $\binom{|\mathcal{Y}|+k-1}{k}$. For a fixed period length, T , k grows linearly with N , and the output alphabet size grows at least as fast as N . The polynomial terms in the MMI decoder analysis actually have the alphabet sizes in their exponent, and thus a straightforward analysis of periodic codes that considers the channel W^k will fail, as these terms become (super) exponential in the code length. Hence, a different analysis of the MMI decoder for periodic codes should be used, taking into account their unique structure.

In general, we assert that most results shown for random codes can be extended to (random) periodic codes, but the proofs should be modified to take the unique structure of the periodic codes into account.

Chapter 7

Broadcasting Common Information

Broadcasting, in everyday terms, means sending the same data to multiple receivers. Radio or television stations broadcast an endless stream of data to many receivers. This common stream is received by all users, but the fidelity of the received data depends on the quality of the channel between the transmitter and receiver. Another situation is when a common data file that should be received reliably is distributed to many receivers. This situation is discussed in Chapter 2, where we presented the static broadcasting concept to allow better receivers to obtain the data file faster. In yet another situation, common data, either a fixed file or a stream, is sent asynchronously to numerous stations, as in the video-on-demand scenario. Schemes such as data carousel or the more sophisticated harmonic transmission [44] (which can be seen as special case of priority encoded transmission scheme [2]) utilize the fact that all receivers should get the same common data to save multiple transmissions, and so maintain a trade-off between the required bandwidth from the shared channel and the reception latency.

This chapter will focus on a novel problem - reliable transmission of a common infinite data stream over a broadcast channel. As in static broadcasting, we want better receivers to reconstruct the data at a higher rate. Unlike static broadcasting, the data is endless, and the receivers need to reconstruct the data in a streamable fashion, i.e., reconstruct successively the information stream. Finally, we consider at the end of this chapter a dual problem of source streaming

to receivers that have different amount of side information.

Note that while an approach that yields different stream rates to the different receivers may not be useful for streams whose timing is crucial, such as video and audio, it can be used to transfer, for example, books and documents where the faster we can reconstruct the first page and then the second page, and so on, the better.

7.1 Common Stream Broadcasting

The regular broadcast channel problem relates to finding the capacity region which is defined by the set of all achievable triplets (R_0, R_1, R_2) . Such a triplet is achievable if we can send both receivers common information at rate R_0 in addition to “private” information at rates R_1 and R_2 to the first and second receivers, respectively [11]. Several subproblems arose from the broadcast scenario, such as finding the capacity region of a degraded broadcast channel and the degraded message set problem [45] which considers the capacity region for $R_2 = 0$. The regular broadcast setting poses some restrictions on the communication system. It assumes that different receivers should/can get different information. To fully utilize the broadcast channel, we should fit the data to be transmitted to the channel. For example, independent messages to the receivers, different levels of distortion to the various receivers as in such as successive refinement [25], etc.

But what can we do with a broadcast channel when we want to transmit the same information to both receivers? One may claim that $(R_1 + R_0, R_2 + R_0)$ is achievable, but this is not true in general. For example, if $R_2 = 0$, then the second receiver will never get information that was transmitted to the first receiver “via R_1 ”, because if it did, this would mean that the first receiver would get this information again, “via R_0 ” leading to a degradation of the effective rate to the first receiver. When $R_2 > 0$ we can ensure that the portion of information that is being transmitted to the first receiver “via R_1 ” will be transmitted to the second receiver “via R_2 ”. For example, assume that we want to send a stream of bits on a broadcast channel with achievable rate $(R_0, R_1, R_2) = (1, 2, 1)$, then we may send the information bits, u_1, u_2, \dots , according to the scheme in Figure 7.1. Indeed,

t	1	2	3	4	5	...
First Only (R_1)	u_1, u_2	u_4, u_5	u_7, u_8	u_{10}, u_{11}	u_{13}, u_{14}	...
Second Only (R_2)	u_1	u_2	u_4	u_5	u_7	...
Both (R_0)	u_3	u_6	u_9	u_{12}	u_{15}	...

Figure 7.1: Sending the same information on a broadcast channel.

in this example we can see that any information bit will, eventually, be received by both receivers, where the first receiver gets 3 bits each time and the second receiver gets 2 bits each time. However, if the data is a stream by nature (such as sample of sound, letters in a book, etc.) then what is important is the length of the data-prefix the receiver has. We can see that although the second receiver holds 8 bits of information at time equals 4 $\{u_1, u_3, u_2, u_6, u_4, u_9, u_5, u_{12}\}$, it has, as prefix, only the first 6 information bits (it does not have, yet, u_7) which leads to effective “stream” rate of 1.5, not 2 bits per unit time!

Definition: A receiver has a *streaming rate* \bar{R} if for any $\epsilon > 0$ there exists T_0 , such that $H(U_t|Y_1^T) < \epsilon$ for any $T > T_0$ and $t < T(\bar{R} - \epsilon)$, where U_1, U_2, \dots , is the uniform IID binary information stream the encoder transmits and Y_1, Y_2, Y_3, \dots are the received symbols.

The definition of the streaming rate implies that each bit in the prefix of length almost $T\bar{R}$ of the source stream can be decoded, with small error probability, given T received symbols.

The following theorem determines an achievable common stream broadcasting capacity region derived from the regular broadcast capacity region.

Theorem 7.1. *Assume that (R_0, R_1, R_2) , $R_1 \geq R_2$, is a point in the capacity region of a broadcast channel, then for any $0 \leq \delta \leq \min(1, \frac{R_1 - R_2}{R_0})$, \bar{R}_1, \bar{R}_2 are achievable streaming rates for the two receivers where*

$$\bar{R}_1 = R_1 + (1 - \delta)R_0 \quad (7.1)$$

$$\bar{R}_2 = R_2 + \delta R_0 + \frac{\bar{R}_2}{R_1}(1 - \delta)R_0 = \frac{\bar{R}_1}{R_1}(R_2 + \delta R_0). \quad (7.2)$$

Proof. We shall prove the theorem by constructing a code that achieves \bar{R}_1, \bar{R}_2 .

The first receiver's code exploits, in addition to its dedicated data, R_1 , part of the common data stream $(1-\delta)R_0$, which yields a stream rate $\bar{R}_1 = R_1 + (1-\delta)R_0$. Hence, a portion of $\frac{(1-\delta)R_0}{R_1 + (1-\delta)R_0}$ of the stream to the first receiver is accessible to the second receiver. The second receiver has a dedicated rate $R_2 + \delta R_0$, using the "traces" of $(1-\delta)R_0$ used by the first receiver, it gets streaming rate of

$$\bar{R}_2 = (R_2 + \delta R_0) \frac{1}{1 - \frac{(1-\delta)R_0}{R_1 + (1-\delta)R_0}} = (R_2 + \delta R_0) \frac{R_1 + (1-\delta)R_0}{R_1}$$

which completes the proof. □

Figure 7.2 depicts the implied common stream broadcasting capacity region assuming $(R_0, R_1, R_2) = (1, 0.5, 0)$.

Figure 7.2: Common stream broadcasting for $(R_0, R_1, R_2) = (1, 0.5, 0)$. Solid line is \bar{R}_2 vs. \bar{R}_1 , dashed line is time-sharing of R_0 and dotted line is R_0 vs. $R_0 + R_1$.

Applying Theorem 7.1 to all points in the regular capacity region yields a region of achievable streaming rates.

Figure 7.3: Common stream broadcasting capacity region of degraded binary channel. Solid line is \bar{R}_2 vs. \bar{R}_1 , dashed line is R_0 vs. R_1 and dotted line is R_0 vs. $R_0 + R_1$.

The capacity region of a degraded binary broadcast channel is plotted in Figure 7.3. The broadcast capacity region of this channel is calculated in (2.6). The streaming capacity region is not convex (time sharing is not applicable for this scheme), and furthermore, it can be observed that the achievable region is greater than simply adding the point $\bar{R}_1 = \bar{R}_2 = \max\{R_0\}$ to the collection of (R_0, R_1) points. The grayed area indicates the “nontrivial” part in the capacity region, i.e., the region that is not contained by simple time sharing of R_0 , and outside the region defined by $\max\{R_0 + \min(R_1, R_2)\}$, which in Figure 7.3 is 0.5. Figures 7.4, 7.5 and 7.6 demonstrate additional examples of the common stream broadcasting capacity region, based on the degraded binary channel, but in each example there is a different bias to R_1 and/or R_2 . In all these plots the solid line is \bar{R}_2 vs. \bar{R}_1 , dashed line is $R_0 + R_2$ vs. R_1 and dotted line is $R_0 + R_2$ vs. $R_0 + R_1$.

Figure 7.4: Common stream broadcasting capacity region of degraded binary channel with added bias to the noisy channel.

A converse to the above theorem follows. The converse is stated for a particular, simple broadcast channel.

Theorem 7.2. *For any triplets of achievable rates (R_0, R_1, R_2) $R_1 \geq R_2$, of a broadcast channel there exists a channel with this point in its capacity region such that if*

$$\bar{R}_1 = R_1 + (1 - \delta)R_0$$

is the maximal possible streaming rate to the first receiver given \bar{R}_2 , then

$$\bar{R}_2 \leq \frac{\bar{R}_1}{R_1}(R_2 + \delta R_0)$$

and $0 \leq \delta \leq \min(1, \frac{R_1 - R_2}{R_0})$.

Figure 7.5: Common stream broadcasting capacity region of degraded binary channel with added bias to the clean channel.

Proof. Consider the broadcast channel¹ whose input symbol is $X = (Y_0, Y_1, Y_2)$, the first receiver gets (Y_0, Y_1) and the second (Y_0, Y_2) . Also $H(Y_i) = R_i$.

Since $R_2 \leq R_1$, the point $\bar{R}_1 = \bar{R}_2 = R_0 + R_2$ is achievable. Also, as $\bar{R}_2 \leq R_0 + R_2$, we have $\bar{R}_1 > \bar{R}_2$ and even $\bar{R}_2 \leq R_0 + R_2 < \bar{R}_1 \leq R_0 + R_1$ with δ in the above region. If $R_0 = 0$ or $\delta = 1$, the assertion is also trivial.

By definition, for any $T > T_0$,

$$I(U^{T\bar{R}_1}; Y_0^T, Y_1^T) \geq T(\bar{R}_1 - \epsilon) = T(R_1 + (1 - \delta)R_0 - \epsilon).$$

Hence $I(U^{T\bar{R}_1}; Y_0^T) \geq T((1 - \delta)R_0 - \epsilon)$. Using the pigeon-hole principle, exists $T > T_0$ such that

$$I(U_{T\bar{R}_1}^{T'\bar{R}_1}; Y_0^{T'}) \geq (T' - T)((1 - \delta)R_0 - 2\epsilon), \quad (7.3)$$

¹This channel is a “clean” broadcast channel, thus the converse holds under separation constraint between the channel coding and streaming coding.

Figure 7.6: Common stream broadcasting capacity region of degraded binary channel with added bias to both channels.

where $T' = \frac{\bar{R}_1}{\bar{R}_2}T$. Using the definition of \bar{R}_2 , and due to the independence of U_S

$$\begin{aligned} T'(\bar{R}_2 - \epsilon) &\leq I(U^{T'\bar{R}_2}; Y_0^{T'}) \\ &\leq I(U^\infty; Y_0^{T'}, Y_2^{T'}) - I(U_{T'\bar{R}_2}^{T'\bar{R}_1}; Y_0^{T'}) + 1 \\ &\leq T'(R_0 + R_2) - (T' - T)((1 - \delta)R_0 - 3\epsilon), \end{aligned}$$

the +1 is since we dropped $U_{T'\bar{R}_2}$, and the last inequality is due to (7.3), and assuming T large enough thus $1 < (T' - T)\epsilon$. Hence

$$\bar{R}_2 - \epsilon \leq R_0 + R_2 - \left(1 - \frac{\bar{R}_2}{\bar{R}_1}\right)((1 - \delta)R_0 - 3\epsilon),$$

which, after some arithmetic, leads to

$$\bar{R}_2 \leq \frac{\bar{R}_1}{R_1 + 3\epsilon}(R_2 + \delta R_0 + 4\epsilon).$$

Since ϵ can be as small as desired, the proof is completed. \square

7.2 Source Streaming to Heterogeneous Receivers

Source coding where the source data is sent to multiple receivers, each with different side information, has many similarities to the broadcast channel problem. In Chapter 4 we considered this source coding situation for the case where fixed finite data is transmitted to the receivers, i.e., the case that is analogous to static broadcasting. We now consider a source coding situation that is analogous to common stream broadcasting.

There are several ways to translate the results obtained above to the scenario of source coding with side information. Possibly the simplest way is to consider the side information, available to each receiver, as the private data it gets, and consider the code bits as common bits, available to all receivers. The rate of the private data to the i th receiver is $I(X; Y_i)$ bits per symbol, and the rate of the common data is 1 bit per unit time. Following these considerations, we provide an explicit calculation of the achievable streaming rates for the two receivers' case of the source coding problem.

Let δ be the parameter that defines how the “common bits” are divided. The first, better receiver for which the conditional entropy $H(X|Y_1)$ is smaller (or $I(X; Y_1)$ is larger) can reconstruct the source at a rate \bar{R}_1 of source symbols per transmitted bit, which must satisfy

$$\bar{R}_1 \cdot H(X) = \bar{R}_1 \cdot I(X; Y_1) + (1 - \delta).$$

This leads to

$$\bar{R}_1 = \frac{1 - \delta}{H(X|Y_1)}. \quad (7.4)$$

The rate of the second receiver must satisfy

$$\bar{R}_2 H(X) = \bar{R}_2 \cdot I(X; Y_2) + \delta + \frac{\bar{R}_2}{\bar{R}_1} (1 - \delta),$$

which leads to

$$\bar{R}_2 = \frac{\delta}{H(X|Y_2) - H(X|Y_1)}. \quad (7.5)$$

These expressions also define the allowable δ :

$$0 \leq \delta \leq 1 - \frac{H(X|Y_1)}{H(X|Y_2)}. \quad (7.6)$$

For the given $H(X|Y_i)$, the possible streaming rates are given by the closure of all points (\bar{R}_1, \bar{R}_2) given by (7.4) and (7.5), for all δ s in the region defined in (7.6).

Chapter 8

Summary and Further Research

In this study we considered the problem of communicating over an unknown channel. Some new concepts were introduced and a variety of subjects related to universal communication were examined.

We began with the new concept of “static broadcasting” in the broadcast channel. The core of this concept is that common finite information is transmitted to all receivers and the rate is defined at the decoder side, while the encoder, which may serve many receivers, does not have a “working rate”. The rate is calculated according to the time each receiver was “online”. Coding theorems, capacity region and bounds on the error probability of this novel setting were developed.

Motivated by the “static broadcasting” approach, we have developed a universal sequential decoding algorithm, based on a universal erasure decoder, and showed that this universal sequential decoder is capable of reliable decoding regardless of the actual underlying DMC. Furthermore the decoding rate tends to the mutual information associated with the code prior and the channel conditional probability, as the size of the information message grows. In addition, we have demonstrated that the universal sequential decoder enables reliable communication in scenarios where the rate is not known in advance, and moreover, there is no expectancy for the effective working rate. These scenarios include the case where there is an unknown amount of side information at the receiver, the case where both the channel and the information message size are unknown, the case where only the encoder knows the channel (and can tune the code for it), and, finally, a combined setting with all the above unknowns. For all these settings

the universal sequential decoder achieves the best rate that can be expected.

The problem of “universal prior” is then discussed. We have shown that the uniform prior is what should be used if the channel is known only to have discrete input. Bounds on the maximum absolute and relative degradation in using the uniform prior as compared with the optimal, unknown prior, are found, and shown to be very small for binary input channels.

Communication through low capacity channels requires codes with long codewords. When communicating through an unknown channel, it may turn out that the channel capacity is infinitely small. Hence the use of codes with unbounded length is required. The complexity of creating, encoding and decoding long codes may be too great. We showed that in the case of low rate codes, we can use periodic codes without significant loss in the achievable transmission rate.

At the end we returned to the broadcast channel and presented yet another new concept for broadcasting common information. This time we looked at possibly infinite information that should be received in a streamable way. This demand led to a new definition of a capacity region, and a coding theorem is proved.

Further Research

The following is a list of issues that can be addressed in further research. Some of these issues extend beyond the scope of the present study, and some may improve the specific results achieved.

Random codes

- In this study we used random codes. For some of the results we did not demonstrate the existence of a specific code that has a small error probability for all channels and/or codewords. For static broadcasting to an infinite set of channels we only showed that the average, over the code ensemble, behaves well. Another example occurs in the transmission of an unknown amount of information, reviewed in Chapter 4. In this case, it is probable that some of the codewords that fit to long messages have common prefix with codewords that fit to short messages, and this yields high probability

of error in the case that one of these long messages is to be sent. Hence, for some of the results in this study one could further investigate and show the existence of a specific code that is simultaneously good for all channels and information messages.

Universal sequential decoder

- In Theorem 3.1 we showed that the effective rate converges to the mutual information. Examining the proof, one can see that for a given information message size, the *ratio* between the mutual information and the expected rate is unbounded. This is because the pre-exponent term is much bigger than the number of codewords when a very large code is used (i.e., very low capacity channel). This may lead to the following question: Is there a universal sequential decoder for which the ratio between the mutual information and the effective rate converges uniformly over all DMCs with a given input alphabet, as the message size goes to infinity? The same question may be asked for all DMCs that share both the input and output alphabets. We conjecture that such a universal sequential decoder *does not* exist.
- How can a decoder utilize partial information on the unknown channel? Partial information may be the knowledge that the channel belongs to a subset of the entire collection of DMCs, e.g., it is known that the channel is a symmetric DMC.

Universal prior

- Proving conjecture 5.12 - The generalized Z-channel achieves the worst degradation w.r.t. the capacity when the uniform prior is used.
- Are there any additional constraints on a maximizing prior other than $P(x) \leq 1 - e^{-1}$ for all x ? That is, given any distribution with the above constraint, is there a DMC such that this prior is its unique capacity achieving prior?

Periodic codes

- Prove the conjecture that the bound in Lemma 6.1 is not tight, and find a better factor than $\frac{A^2}{\log e}$. Also improve the quadratic bound of Lemma 6.2 to enable a better bound on μ as function of t .

Stream broadcasting

- We did not provide a complete converse to the common stream broadcasting coding theorem. Note that a converse is not available, in general, for the regular broadcast channel. A possible task can be to prove a separation theorem. Proving the converse, even for degraded broadcast channels, will enhance our result.
- Extend the results to more than two channels.
- If the (slower) decoder has a finite memory, we can still achieve streaming rate $\bar{R}_1 = R_1 + (1 - \delta)R_0$ and $\bar{R}_2 = R_2 + \delta R_0$ simply by time sharing of R_0 between the 2 receivers. Can we do better?

These questions and many other are still open, making universal communication a challenging area for further research.

Appendix A

On Random Coding Error Exponents

A.1 Random Coding Error Exponents

Random coding error exponents may depend on the random code ensemble and on the decoder. There are two types of code ensembles, and two types of decoders that we shall examine.

- Ensemble construction: Choosing each codeword from a type or choose each symbol IID.
- Decoder: Using an ML decoder or an MMI decoder.

Assume a DMC W with input alphabet \mathcal{X} and output alphabet \mathcal{Y} . The error exponent for random ensemble of constant composition codes of rate R , where each codeword is independently chosen from T_Q is

$$E_r(R, W, T_Q) = \min_V D(V||W|Q) + |I(Q; V) - R|^+. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

This error exponent is for both ML decoder and MMI decoder [18], and it is tight¹, as can be proved by its relation to the sphere-packing bound, see Lemma A.3.

For the random ensemble where each symbol at each codeword is chosen independently with distribution $Q(x)$, the error exponent using ML decoder is

$$E_r(R, W, Q) = \min_{0 \leq \rho \leq 1} E_0(\rho, W, Q) - \rho R.$$

¹A random coding error exponent is tight if it equals the exponential behavior of the average error probability over the ensemble.

where $E_0(\rho, W, Q)$ is defined in (2.3). This bound is also tight over the random ensemble² [31].

Below is a derivation of the random coding error exponent for the ensemble of IID chosen symbols with an MMI decoder.

Theorem A.1. *Given a DMC W with finite input and output alphabets. Assume a random code \mathcal{C} , with $M = 2^{NR}$ codewords of length N randomly chosen independently with distribution $Q(\mathbf{x}) = \prod Q(x_i)$. Then, the error exponent when using an MMI decoder is*

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_r^u(R, W, Q) & \tag{A.2} \\
 & = \min_{\substack{V, P=V', P' \\ I(V; P) \leq I(V'; P')}} D(V||W|P) + D(P||Q) + |I(V'; P') + D(P'||Q) - R|^+.
 \end{aligned}$$

Also, this error exponent over the ensemble is tight.

Proof. All summations to follow over (conditional) types are over all possible (conditional) types for sequences of length N .

$$\begin{aligned}
 \bar{P}_e & = \sum_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}^N} Q(\mathbf{x}) \sum_{\mathbf{y} \in \mathcal{Y}^N} W(\mathbf{y}|\mathbf{x}) \Pr(\text{error}|\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \\
 & = \sum_{P, V} Q(T_P) W(\mathbf{y} \in T_V(\mathbf{x})|\mathbf{x} \in T_P) \Pr(\text{error}|\mathbf{x} \in T_P, \mathbf{y} \in T_V(\mathbf{x})). \tag{A.3}
 \end{aligned}$$

An error occurs if there is a codeword $\mathbf{x}' \in T_{P'}$ such that $\mathbf{y} \in T_{V'}(\mathbf{x}')$ and $I(P'; V') \geq I(P; V)$ (ties are taken as error). Using union bound over all possible $M - 1$ codewords, and bounding the probability by 1, leads to

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \Pr(\text{error}|\mathbf{x} \in T_P, \mathbf{y} \in T_V(\mathbf{x})) \\
 & \leq \min \left\{ 1, (M - 1) \sum_{\substack{V', P' \\ I(P; V) \leq I(P'; V')}} Q(\{\mathbf{x}' : \mathbf{x}' \in T_{P'}, \mathbf{y} \in T_{V'}(\mathbf{x}')\}) \right\} \tag{A.4}
 \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$Q(\{\mathbf{x}' : \mathbf{x}' \in T_{P'}, \mathbf{y} \in T_{V'}(\mathbf{x}')\}) \leq 2^{-N(I(V'; P') + D(P'||Q))}. \tag{A.5}$$

²In [31] it was showed that the average error probability over the IID ensemble is upper bounded by $O(\sqrt{N})2^{-NE_r}$.

Furthermore

$$Q(T_P) \leq 2^{-ND(P||Q)} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

and

$$W(\mathbf{y} \in T_V(\mathbf{x}) | \mathbf{x} \in T_P) \leq 2^{-N(D(V||W|P))}. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Combining (A.3) through (A.7) and further bounding the summations by the number of terms (which is polynomial with N) times the maximal term yields the error exponent in (A.2).

The bounds in (A.5), (A.6) and (A.7) are exponentially tight. Lemma A.2 shows that the clipped union-bound is tight up to factor of 2, which completes the proof. \square

This error exponent is positive for $R < I(Q; W)$. A simple bound to E_r^u is

$$E_r^u(R, W, Q) \leq \min_{V, P} D(V||W|P) + D(P||Q) + |I(V; P) - R|^+. \quad (\text{A.8})$$

We conjecture that this bound is tight.

The derivation above can be used to derive the other random coding error exponents. For the IID symbols ensemble with ML decoder it leads to the following presentation of the random coding error exponent:

$$E_r(R, W, Q) = \min_{V, P} D(V||W|P) + D(P||Q) + |I(V; P) + D(P||Q) - R|^+. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Using [61], we can write

$$E_r(R, W, T_Q) = \max_P \max_{0 \leq \rho \leq 1} E_0(\rho, W, P) - \rho R - (1 + \rho)D(Q||P). \quad (\text{A.10})$$

The three error exponents have the following order

$$E_r(R, W, T_Q) \geq E_r(R, W, T) \geq E_r^u(R, W, Q). \quad (\text{A.11})$$

For the maximizing Q , using (A.10)

$$\max_Q E_r(R, W, T_Q) = \max_Q E_r(R, W, T) \geq \max_Q E_r^u(R, W, Q). \quad (\text{A.12})$$

We conjecture that the last inequality is equality.

Example for the Random Coding Error Exponents

Assume W is a clean channel, then we have

$$E_r(R, W, T_Q) = E_r(R, W, Q) = H(Q) - R.$$

Hence the probability that there is another codeword that equals the sent codeword is the dominant part of these decoding error probability³. But

$$E_r^u(R, W, Q) = \min_P D(P||Q) + |H(P) - R|^+.$$

For $R = 0$ this yields $E_r^u(0, W, Q) = \log \frac{1}{\max_x Q(x)}$. This means that the decoding error probability is dominated by the probability that the sent codeword is a repetition of one symbol. An MMI decoder will never correctly decode (unless it ties with all other codewords) such a codeword because it has zero mutual information with any channel's outcome.

For the maximizing Q , which is uniform distribution in this example, all three error exponents equal to $\log |\mathcal{X}| - R$,

Example - The MMI decoder is not optimal

Here is an example of why the MMI decoder is inferior to the ML decoder even for constant composition code. The MMI decoder has exponentially tight performance as ML decoder for the constant composition ensemble average, it is not the case for other ensemble or specific codes such as the IID ensemble. Assume erasure channel and code with 2 codewords and a possible outcome of the channel:

$$\begin{aligned} X_1 &= 10101010 \\ Y &= 1010EEEE \\ X_2 &= 11110000 \end{aligned}$$

Of course X_1 was the one that we sent, but $I(X_1, Y) = 1/2$ and $I(X_2; Y) = 1$!

Note that in the erasure channel, and constant composition code, any output sequence that leads to a tie in the ML decoder leads to a tie in the MMI decoder, but not vice versa. For example, $X_1 = 10$, $X_2 = 01$ and $Y = 0E$.

³These are the only misdecoding an ML decoder will make, but an MMI decoder with constant composition code can have other kinds of errors as shown in the examples to follow.

An MMI decoder can have a decoding mistake even when using constant composition code over a clean channel. For example, $X_1 = 1122333$, $X_2 = 2211333$ and $Y = X_1$. We have $I(X_1; Y) = I(X_2; Y)$. Note that this can happen only if there are at least two input symbols with the same probability in the type.

A.2 Tightness of the Union Bound

The derivations of the random coding error exponents in the previous section used the (clipped) union bound. In order to prove the tightness of these error exponents, we should prove that the used union bounds are tight “enough”. In this section we show that the clipped union bound is tight up to the factor of two.

Let A_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$, be a collection of events with probability $\Pr(A_i)$, then the well-known union bound states that

$$U = \Pr\left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n A_i\right) \leq \sum_{i=1}^n \Pr(A_i) = S.$$

The “clipped” union bound is simply $U \leq \min(S, 1)$.

In general $S/n \leq U \leq S$ and in case the events A_i are dependent, we may have both extremes: $U = S$ if the events are mutually exclusive, or $U = S/n$ if all the events are the same.

The following lemma demonstrates a lower bound on U given S that is valid in case of possibly dependent events, as long as they are pair-wise independent.

Lemma A.2. *If the events $A_1 \dots A_n$ are pair-wise independent then:*

$$U \geq \begin{cases} S(1 - \frac{S}{2}) & \text{for } S < 1 \\ \frac{1}{2} & \text{for } S \geq 1. \end{cases}$$

In particular $U \geq \frac{1}{2} \min(S, 1)$.

Proof. We shall denote by $P_i = \Pr(A_i)$, $S_k = \sum_{i=1}^k P_i$ and $U_k = \Pr(\bigcup_{i=1}^k A_i)$. We

have

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_{k+1} &= S_k + P_{k+1} \\
 U_{k+1} &\stackrel{(a)}{=} U_k + P_{k+1} - \Pr(A_{k+1} \cap (\bigcup_{i=1}^k A_i)) \\
 &= U_k + P_{k+1} - \Pr(\bigcup_{i=1}^k (A_i \cap A_{k+1})) \\
 &\stackrel{(b)}{\geq} U_k + P_{k+1} - \sum_{i=1}^k \Pr(A_i \cap A_{k+1}) \\
 &\stackrel{(c)}{=} U_k + P_{k+1} - \sum_{i=1}^k \Pr(A_i) P_{k+1} \\
 &= U_k + P_{k+1}(1 - S_k) \\
 &\geq U_k + P_{k+1}(1 - S_k - P_{k+1}/2) \\
 &= U_k + \int_0^{P_{k+1}} 1 - (S_k + x) \, dx \\
 &\stackrel{(d)}{\geq} \int_0^{S_{k+1}} 1 - x \, dx \\
 &= S_{k+1}(1 - \frac{S_{k+1}}{2}),
 \end{aligned}$$

where (a) due to $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A \cap B)$, (b) using the regular union bound, (c) since the events are pair-wise independent and (d) by induction over previous steps.

The monotonicity of U leads to the desired result. \square

A.3 Structured Random Codes Are Better

In finding bounds on the error probability, we assume that the codewords are chosen independently, and a bound on the error probability between two codewords is extended to the entire code using union bound, e.g., (A.4). For these bounds to be valid, it is sufficient for the codewords to be chosen pair-wise independently [30, 68].

An example for an ensemble of codes where the codewords are not even pair-wise independent, is one where all codewords in each code are the same. In this case $P_e = 1 - M^{-1} \rightarrow 1$.

As shown by Lemma A.2, the union bound is tight in case the events are pair-wise independent. In bounding the error probability, the error events are of the type: we sent \mathbf{x} and received \mathbf{x}' . Hence, in order to make these events pair-wise independent, the codewords should be triplet-wise independent.

So, in case the codewords are “just” pair-wise independent, the union bound is valid but may not be tight. Hence, for such ensembles, the average error probability may be even smaller.

For example, assume a clean channel and input distribution Q . In this case, as shown, $E_r(R, W, T_Q) = H(Q) - R$. We build an ensemble in the following manner: For each $\mathbf{x} \in T_Q$, all codewords equal \mathbf{x} in probability $|T_Q|^{-2}$. Otherwise the codewords are randomly selected under the constraint that no two are the same. As can be verified, the codewords are pair-wise independent in this ensemble, and the error probability equals the probability to have a code with all codewords the same, i.e., $|T_Q|^{-1}$, which leads to error exponent $E(R) = H(Q)$, which does not depend on the rate.

A.4 Best Distribution of Codewords

The sphere packing bound

$$E_{sp}(R, W, Q) = \min_{\substack{V \\ I(Q;V) \leq R}} D(V||W|Q)$$

is an upper bound on the error exponent of each code constructed of codewords from type T_Q , and, of course an upper bound to $E_r(R, W, T_Q)$ defined in (A.1).

The two error exponents have the following relation

$$E_r(R, W, T_Q) = \min_{R' \geq R} E_{sp}(R', W, Q) + R' - R. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

This leads to the following

Lemma A.3. *The random coding error exponent $E_r(R, W, T_Q)$ is a tight bound for the average error probability over the constant composition random ensemble.*

Proof. Assume $\tilde{E}(R)$ is the true error exponent for the ensemble average. Then the average error probability of code with $M = 2^{NR}$ codewords is $\bar{P}_e(M) =$

$2^{-N\tilde{E}(R)}$. As the codewords are chosen independently, using the union bound, for $M' > M$, we get $\bar{P}_e(M') \leq M'M^{-1}2^{-N\tilde{E}(R)}$. Hence for $R' > R$, $\tilde{E}(R') \geq \tilde{E}(R) + R - R'$. However, given that $E_{sp}(R')$ is an upper bound,

$$\tilde{E}(R') \leq \min_{R' \geq R} E_{sp}(R') - R' + R. \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Comparing this with (A.13) completes the proof. \square

Following Lemma A.3 and its proof, we have another lemma:

Lemma A.4. *For any probability distribution over T_P , $E_r(R, W, T_P)$ is an upper bound on the error exponent of an ensemble of codes, whose codewords are chosen independently with that distribution.*

For any distribution, $Q(\mathbf{x})$ over \mathcal{X}^N there exists a type P such that $Q(T_P) > (N + 1)^{-|\mathcal{X}|}$. Combining this with the above corollary leads to the following:

Corollary A.5. *Uniform selection over a complete type achieves the best random coding error exponent.*

Using the above results, we may have an alternative proof of Lemma 5.13, which states that given a channel, W , and two prior distributions P and P' , then

$$\frac{I(P; W)}{I(P'; W)} \geq \min_x \frac{P(x)}{P'(x)}.$$

Alternative proof of Lemma 5.13. It is sufficient to show that a random code chosen from T_P^n is better (or equal) than a random code chosen from $T_{P'}^{n'}$ where $n = n' \max_x \frac{P(x)}{P'(x)}$. Due to these relations, there exists a sequence of length $n - n'$ such that adding it to each sequence in $T_{P'}$ yields a sequence in T_P . Adding this sequence to all codewords chosen from $T_{P'}$ will not change the achieved error probability using the ML decoder, but Lemma A.4 states that if we choose the codewords uniformly over T_P we will have an error exponent no worse than that, which completes the proof of Lemma 5.13. \square

Appendix B

Sequential Almost Constant Composition Codes

The motivation for having a constant composition code is attributable to the fact that such (random) codes may yield better error exponents¹. For examples see Chapter 2 and Appendix A.

In the setting we examine here, the codes are infinite length and a decoder may only require a specific prefix of a codeword. However, it is not possible to have a codeword such that all its prefixes have the same prior (unless the codeword is constructed from a single symbol that repeats itself), and if we wish that for any l the prefix of length l of all codewords will belong to some type, e.g., T_{P_l} , will lead to equal codewords since the $l + 1$ th symbol for all codewords must be the one that “converts” P_l to P_{l+1} .

So, a constant composition code cannot be found with the desired prefix properties, hence, a certain amount of flexibility should be allowed. There are many possibilities to achieve this, a selection of which are listed below:

- Each prefix of each codeword will be from almost the same type, i.e., the prior distribution of the prefixes will be close to the desired type. The longer the prefix, the closer it is to the desired prior. The concept *closer*

¹Constant composition codes have better or equal error exponent with respect to IID random codes. Nonexponential arguments may be in favor of nonconstant composition codes - probably the *best* code for a given channel, length, and number of codewords is not constant composition. If we would have known the channel and used the optimal prior, it is known that random coding using IID or constant composition have the same exponent [61] for block codes. However, as we are not tuned to the channel,(random) constant composition codes are likely to be better.

can have several interpretations, including small divergence.

- An enhancement of the above, where instead of prefixes we want to be near the desired type for any interval. The longer the interval, the closer we want to be, again, in metrics such as the divergence.
- Each codeword will consist of short intervals, where each such interval is of the desired type. Of course, any interval which begins and ends at multiplicities of the short interval length will have exactly the desired type.

It is obvious that the three options above appear in decreasing order, i.e., the set defined by the third option is included in the set defined in the second option, which is included in the set defined in the first option.

In the sequel we focus on the first possibility. Assume an IID source with distribution P over the alphabet \mathcal{X} . Given a sequence of that source, \mathbf{x} , denote by $P_{\mathbf{x}}^n$ the type of its n -length prefix.

The probability that a prefix of length n has a type, say Q , is upper bounded by $\Pr(P_{\mathbf{x}}^n = Q) \leq 2^{-nD(Q||P)}$. As there are less than $(n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}|-1}$ different types for n -length sequences, the probability that the n -length prefix of the IID random sequence will belong to a type that is close to P up to ϵ in divergence sense, i.e., $D(P_{\mathbf{x}}^n||P) \leq \epsilon$, can be bounded by

$$\Pr(D(P_{\mathbf{x}}^n||P) \leq \epsilon) \geq 1 - (n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}|-1} 2^{-n\epsilon}. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Define $N_0 = \lceil \frac{K}{\log|\mathcal{X}|} \rceil$. We can assume that any decoder may try to decode only after receiving N_0 symbols, hence prefixes shorter than N_0 can have no type constraint. Given a set of allowed distances $\{\epsilon_n\}$, an infinite sequence is “good” if for all $n > N_0$, the type of the n -length prefix is close to P , up to ϵ_n . The probability that a sequence is “good” is

$$P_{\text{OK}} = \Pr(\forall n \geq N_0, D(P_{\mathbf{x}}^n||P) \leq \epsilon_n).$$

Using (B.1) it can be bounded as follows

$$P_{\text{OK}} \geq 1 - \sum_{n \geq N_0} (n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}|-1} 2^{-n\epsilon_n}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Setting

$$\epsilon_n = \frac{2|\mathcal{X}|\log(n+1)}{n} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

will yield

$$P_{\text{OK}} \geq 1 - \sum_{n \geq N_0} (n+1)^{-(|\mathcal{X}|+1)} > \frac{1}{2} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

as $|\mathcal{X}| \geq 2$ and $\sum_{n>1} n^{-3} < \frac{1}{2}$.

Now, for any $\delta > 0$ exists² $\epsilon > 0$ small enough (depending on P) such that if $D(Q||P) < \epsilon$ then

$$Q(x) \geq (1 - \delta)P(x) \quad (\text{B.5})$$

for each $x \in \mathcal{X}$. For large enough K we have $\epsilon_n \leq \epsilon$ for any $n > N_0$.

The random almost constant composition code is generated by choosing the codewords as in the IID case, under the condition that it must be “good”.

Bounding $D(Q||P)$ by zero, and $D(V||W|Q) \geq (1 - \delta)D(V||W|P)$, equations (3.16), (3.17) and (3.20) can be modified for this for almost constant composition random code:

$$\Pr(A_n) \leq \max_{\substack{V \\ I(P;V) < \tilde{R}_n}} 2(n+1)^{|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-1} \exp_2\{-n(1 - \delta)D(V||W|P)\} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$\Pr(B_n) \leq \max_{\substack{V \\ I(P;V) \geq \tilde{R}_n}} 4(n+1)^{2|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-2} \exp_2\{-n[(1 - \delta)D(V||W|P) + R'_n - R_n]\} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$\Pr(U_n) \leq \max_{\substack{V \\ I(P;V) \leq R'_n}} 4(n+1)^{2|\mathcal{X}||\mathcal{Y}|-2} \exp_2\{-n[(1 - \delta)D(V||W|P) + \tilde{R}_n - R_n]\}, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

where the factors 2 and 4 are because the codewords are chosen from a subspace with probability greater than half. Hence the probability that such a codeword will be chosen is up to twice more than in the IID case. We should have a factor of 2 for the transmitted word and a factor of 2 for the opponents [68].

²This can be shown by using Pinsker’s inequality $D(P(x)||Q(x)) \geq \frac{\log e}{2} (\sum_x |P(x) - Q(x)|)^2$ that implies for each x , $\frac{Q(x)}{P(x)} \geq 1 - \sqrt{\frac{2\epsilon}{P^2(x)\log e}}$, which leads to $\delta = \max_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \sqrt{\frac{2\epsilon}{P^2(x)\log e}}$.

Continuing as in Section 3.3, and noting that as K grows, δ can tend to zero, the sequential decoder for the almost constant composition codes can attain the performance stated in Theorem 3.1.

As in the IID solution, tradeoffs between rate and error probability may be the outcome of choosing differently \tilde{R}_n and R'_n . When looking at rates smaller than the mutual information, as can be noted from the differences between (B.6)-(B.8) and their equivalents in Section 3.3, the almost constant composition codes yield better error exponents compared to the IID codes. The improvement in the error exponents, in this case, is similar to the improvement shown in Appendix A between $E_r(R, W, T_P)$ and $E_r^u(R, W, P)$.

Appendix C

Proofs of Lemmas in Chapter 5

Proof of Lemma 5.6: Assume that out of all functions that satisfy the monotonicity and integrability conditions of the lemma, $f(x)$ leads to the maximal possible value of t , denoted t^* . Since $\frac{1}{1-x} > 1$ for $0 < x \leq 1$, and $t^* < 1$, we can set $f(x) = c$ for $x > t^*$, where c is a constant chosen to satisfy $\int_0^1 f(x)dx = 1$ and will be no greater than $f(t^*)$. Define a new function $g(x)$ that satisfies the conditions, as follows:

$$g(x) = \begin{cases} f(x) + f(x + \frac{v}{2}) - c & \text{for } x \leq \frac{v}{2} \\ c & \text{for } x > \frac{v}{2} \end{cases},$$

where $v = \inf\{x | f(x) = c\}$.

As $\frac{1}{1-x}$ increases monotonically, if $g(x) \neq f(x)$ the value of t that corresponds to $g(x)$ is greater than t^* , which contradicts the assumption. Hence $g(x) = f(x)$, though this can happen only if $v = 0$ and then $f(x) = c$, which actually leads to $f(x) = 1$. Solving for t with $f(x) = 1$ leads to $t^* = 1 - e^{-1}$. \square

Proof of Lemma 5.7: It is sufficient to show that if $z_0(\tilde{u}) = d_0(\tilde{u})$, then $z'_0(\tilde{u}) \leq d'_0(\tilde{u})$ with equality if and only if $z_0(\cdot) = d_0(\cdot)$. Now, $z_0(\tilde{u}) = d_0(\tilde{u})$ means

$$\log \frac{1}{1 - \tilde{u}p} = \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} q_0(y) \log \frac{q_0(y)}{\tilde{u}q_1(y) + (1 - \tilde{u})q_0(y)}. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

Using Jensen's inequality and taking the exponent of both sides

$$\frac{1}{1 - \tilde{u}p} \leq \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} q_0(y) \frac{q_0(y)}{\tilde{u}q_1(y) + (1 - \tilde{u})q_0(y)}. \quad (\text{C.2})$$

As $\log(\cdot)$ is strictly convex, equality in the last equation will hold only if q_1 and q_0 fit the Z-channel (actually it might fit an “effective Z-channel” where several output symbols have the same distribution as the '0' symbol in the Z-channel, and a similar situation for the '1' symbol). Now

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{u}z'_0(\tilde{u}) &= \frac{\tilde{u}p}{1 - \tilde{u}p} = \frac{1}{1 - \tilde{u}p} - 1 \\ &\leq -1 + \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} q_0(y) \frac{q_0(y)}{\tilde{u}q_1(y) + (1 - \tilde{u})q_0(y)} \\ &= \sum_{y \in \mathcal{Y}} q_0(y) \frac{\tilde{u}q_0(y) - \tilde{u}q_1(y)}{\tilde{u}q_1(y) + (1 - \tilde{u})q_0(y)} = \tilde{u}d'_0(\tilde{u}), \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof. \square

Lemma 5.7 leads to the following interesting inequality for the divergence:

Corollary C.1. *For any distributions $p_1(y), p_0(y)$, let p be such that*

$$D(p_0||p_1) = \log \frac{1}{1 - p},$$

then

$$D(p_0||up_1 + (1 - u)p_0) \leq \log \frac{1}{1 - up}$$

for all $0 \leq u \leq 1$.

This corollary is stronger than the straightforward usage of the log-function monotonicity which is the above inequality with $p = 1$.

Proof of Lemma 5.8: Using (5.13) we have

$$0 = I_Z(\tilde{u}) - I(\tilde{u}) = \int_{\tilde{u}}^1 \frac{\tilde{u}}{u^2} [z_0(u) - d_0(u)] du.$$

Hence, exists a point u , $\tilde{u} \leq u \leq 1$ such that $z_0(u) = d_0(u)$. As a result, due to Lemma 5.7, $z_0(u) \geq d_0(u)$ for all $u < \tilde{u}$. Using (5.13) again, completes the proof. \square

Proof of Lemma 5.11: We need to prove that

$$C \leq \log \frac{1}{\max_x P^*(x)} \quad (= H_\infty(P^*)) \quad .$$

Given that the channel law is $W(y|x)$, the output distribution, corresponding to the input distribution $P^*(x)$, is $Q^*(y) = \sum_x P^*(x)W(y|x)$. It is well known that for each x (such that $P^*(x) > 0$) $C = D(W(\cdot||x)||Q^*)$. Now, as $Q^*(y) \geq P^*(x)W(y|x)$ for each y , we have $C = D(W(\cdot||x)||Q^*) \leq -\log P^*(x)$ which completes the proof. \square

Proof of Lemma 5.13: Define $r = \max_x \frac{P'(x)}{P(x)}$, then the lemma claims that

$$I(P'; W) \leq rI(P; W).$$

Given that for each x , $P'(x) \leq rP(x)$ it is sufficient to show that the function

$$\tilde{I}(P; W) = \sum_{x,y} P(x)W(y|x) \log \frac{W(y|x)}{\sum_x W(y|x) \frac{P(x)}{\sum_{x'} P(x')}}.$$

is *increasing* w.r.t. each $P(x)$ (without the constraint $\sum_x P(x) = 1$).

Define $Q(y) = \sum_x W(y|x) \frac{P(x)}{\sum_{x'} P(x')}$, then, for each x_0 we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\tilde{I}(P; W)}{dP(x_0)} &= \sum_y W(y|x_0) \log \frac{W(y|x_0)}{Q(y)} - \\ &\quad \sum_{x,y} P(x)W(y|x) \frac{1}{Q(y)} \frac{dQ(y)}{dP(x_0)} \\ &= D(W(y|x_0)||Q(y)) - \\ &\quad \sum_{x,y} \frac{P(x)W(y|x)}{Q(y)} \frac{W(y|x_0) - Q(y)}{\sum_{x'} P(x')} \\ &= D(W(y|x_0)||Q(y)) \geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

which completes the proof. \square

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